

D3.3 A generic framework for selection of the most promising CCUS value chains

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Authorisation

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No industry has committed at this stage to implement the scenarios presented in the deliverable D3.3. The scenarios presented here, while based on an industrial reality on the ground, are forward-looking scenarios that explore the potential of CCUS in each of these regions

Executive summary

This report proposes a framework for initial screening of the most promising national and cross-border CCUS value chains at their very early stage of development and applies it to eight case studies from the Baltic Sea and Mediterranean Sea regions conducted by the Horizon Europe CCUS-ZEN project.

The main objective of this report was to identify the most promising CCUS value chains for the CCUS ZEN regions based on SWOT analysis and to establish a generic framework for the selection of the most prospective CCUS value chains, based on the high-level screening methodology established in WP1 and integrated with WP2 analyses.

Additional objectives of this report are to 1) document the methodology used for the SWOT analyses and extend the framework developed in WP1 for high-level screening to include selection of the most prospective CCUS value chains; 2) reveal which CO₂ use options will permit use the most captured CO₂, will produce the highest revenues, will be the most environmentally friendly and will provide the products with the longest life cycle for CO₂ emission storage, and 3) compare the storage sites for the largest storage capacity, safety, injectivity, location and economic effectivity, and their storage readiness level (SRL). Availability of CO₂ transport infrastructure and possibility for reuse will be strong side of the projects.

Technical and non-technical data were first collected and integrated into a common GIS project for eight countries in the Baltic region and five countries in the Mediterranean region. To apply SWOT analysis to the prospective CCUS cluster projects, internal and external groups of parameters were first developed. Internal technical groups (strengths and weaknesses) include 1) CO₂ emission plants, 2) CO₂ storage sites, 3) available and planned infrastructure, and 4) CO₂ use options. An external technical group includes 1) characteristics of the area around the storage site, and non-technical external groups include social and political development, international and national regulations, MRV (Monitoring Reporting and Verification) and accounting readiness, financial, readiness of CCUS value chain, CCUS in industrial strategy plan and interaction of CCUS with other decarbonization technologies which were analysed for opportunities and threats.

The developed framework includes 25 internal quantitative technical parameters and 14 external qualitative parameters, which were collected for eight CCUS value chains in two sea regions. These internal and external parameters were the base for creating the SWOT matrix of CCUS value chains strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. For the qualitative parameters, an equivalent quantitative scaling method was designed to be able to include external parameters in the quantitative SWOT analysis.

However, the export of CO₂ to offshore storage sites needs CO₂ storage regulations to be implemented internationally (London Protocol Amendment to article 6) and regionally (Helsinki and Barcelona Conventions), in addition to national regulations and permits needed for CO₂ storage both in onshore and offshore sites.

Despite these differences, it is possible to perform a unified quantitative analysis for all projects (both onshore and offshore) by utilising common internal technical factors and a shortlist of external technical and non-technical parameters.

Here, we reported the semiquantitative results of the analysis, the framework for the quantitative SWOT analysis, and data collected for quantitative analysis.

All the proposed projects have opportunities for implementation but need a considerable amount of work to be done starting from international and national political cooperation and development, regulatory and permitting changes, CCUS technologies development and implementation, cooperation of national stakeholders and governmental support of CCUS value chains. Cooperation with other technologies is also needed. The number of CCS PCI projects available in both studied regions is a good start for the possible development and implementation of the proposed CCUS value chains.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND UNITS

Abbreviations

CCS – CO₂ Capture and Storage

CCU – Carbon Capture and Utilisation

CCUS – CO₂ Capture, Utilization and Storage

CO₂ – Carbon Dioxide

CP – Cement Plant

DAC – Direct Air Capture

DEA – Danish Energy Agency

D1.2 – Deliverable 1.2 of CCUS ZEN project WP1

DOGF – Depleted Oil & Gas field

DSA – Deep saline aquifer

EU – European Union

IPCEI – Important Project of Common European Interest

ISO – International Standard Organisation

GHG – Greenhouse Gas

GIS – Geographic Information System

QGIS – is an open-source geographic information system

LCO₂ – liquid CO₂

MRV – Monitoring, Reporting and Verification

N - Number

NECP – National Energy and Climate Plans

NCT – National Carbon Tax

PP – Power Plant

SPA –Special Protection Area

T&S – Transport and Storage

WP3 – Work Package 3

WTE – Waste-to-energy

Units

m – metre

g/l – gram per litre

kg – kilogram

kg/m³ – kilograms per cubic metre

kg/s – kilograms per second

km – kilometer

km² – square kilometre

kt – kiloton

kt/y – kiloton per year

kW – kilowatt

kW/h – kilowatt per hour

l – litre

MPa – mega Pascal

Mt – million tonnes

Mt/y – million tonnes per year

MW – megawatt

MWh – megawatt hours

m – metre

m/s – metres per second

mD – milli Darcy

t – tonne

t/hr – tonne per hour

T, °C – temperature by Celsius

TJ – Terajoule

W – watt

W/m² K – watts per square meter per kelvin, SI unit for heat transfer coefficient

1 Introduction

The main objectives of the D3.3 is to identify the most promising CCUS value chains for the CCUS ZEN regions based on SWOT analysis and to establish a generic framework for the selection of the most prospective CCUS value chains, based on the high-level screening methodology established in WP1 and integrated with WP2 analyses.

Additional objectives of this report is to:

- ▷ Document the methodology used for the SWOT analyses and extend the framework developed in WP1 for high-level screening to include selection of the most prospective CCUS value chains.
- ▷ Reveal which CO₂ use options will permit use the most captured CO₂, will produce the highest revenues, will be the most environmentally friendly and will provide the products with the longest life cycle for CO₂ emission storage.
- ▷ Compare the storage sites for the largest storage capacity, safety, injectivity, location and economic effectivity, and their storage readiness level (SRL). Availability of CO₂ transport infrastructure and possibility for reuse will be strong side of the projects.

2 Data and Methods

2.1 Data

Technical data collected in WP1 and reported in D1.1 and D1.2 (Ringstad et al, 2023, Gravaud et al, 2024) and nontechnical data collected in by WP2 and partly reported in (Honegger et al, 2024), were used for WP3 analysis. Technical and non-technical data were first collected and integrated into a common GIS project for eight countries in the Baltic region and five countries in the Mediterranean region by WP1 (Figure 2-1). Technical data includes layers with large CO₂ emissions sources, CO₂ storage sites, available pipeline infrastructure and Natura 2000 areas (Figure 2-2, Figure 2-3).

To analyse CO₂ use options in the research and developing phase, data collected for the proposed value chains and reported in D1.1, D1.2 and D3.1 were used (Ringstad et al, 2023, Gravaud et al, 2024, Shogenova et al, 2024).

Additionally, recent publications and reports including 130-133 CCU products analysed in the long lists and revealed the best CCU products in the short lists (8-15 products) were applied (EC, 2019, Chauvy et al, 2019 and Shokrollahi et al, 2024). Results of these studies are summarised in the methods.

Technical data includes layers with large CO₂ emissions sources, CO₂ storage sites, available pipeline infrastructure and Natura 2000 areas (Figure 2-2, Figure 2-3).

Eight large CCUS cluster projects, four in each studied region (Table 2-1), were selected by WP1 (Gravaud et al, 2024) for the more detailed technical analysis, integration with CO₂ use options and non-technical parameters (Figure 2-1).

Figure 2-1 Two CCUS ZEN Regions with location of CO₂ storage sites (red) and eight projects selected for analysis in WP3.

Figure 2-2 Location of 4 Baltic projects on the map with technical data

Figure 2-3 Location of 4 Mediterranean projects on the map with technical data

Table 2-1 Technical parameters of the 8 value chains in the Baltic Sea and Mediterranean Sea Regions selected in D1.2 for WP3 analysis (updated by WP3).

Region	Value chain name	Involved countries	Total produced CO ₂ emissions, Mt/y	Number of emission sources	Number of emission clusters	CO ₂ captured/CO ₂ used, Mt/y	Storage sites	Number of storage sites	Total CO ₂ storage capacity, Mt	Total years for storage	Distance from plants to storage sites, km
Baltic-1	Baltic Lat-Lit-onshore	Latvia Lithuania	4.25	6	2	4.04/ 0.4	North Blidene, Blidene and Dobele	3	403	> 40	9-150
Baltic-2	DE DK SWE Jutland network	Germany Denmark Sweden	22.66	33	9	20.14/ 6.1	Gassum, Voldum, Jammerbugt Inez, Bifrost, Greensand, Lisa, Thorning	8	928	> 40	5-750
Baltic-3	Copenhagen	Germany Denmark Sweden	5.9	16	4	5.62/ 0.56	Rødby, Havnsø, Stenlille	3	657	> 40	5-200
Baltic-4	North Poland onshore	Poland	8.19	11	4	7.78/ 0.78	Konary J, Kamionki K	2	381	52	4.2-38.2
Med-1 (M-1)	Soma - İzmir Aliağa - Prinos	Türkiye Greece	40.0	16	2	18.64/ 5.59	Prinos	1	1000	25.0	120-360
Med -2 (M-2)	Ebro offshore	Spain and France	23.82	32	3	9.77/ 2.93	Castellon	1	200.0	20	50-470
Med -3 (M-3)	Beaucaire	France	1.17	2	1	0.833/ 0.25	Haut d'Albaron	1	34	29	27
Med -4 (M-4)	South Italy network and Athens, Greece	Italy and Greece	41,1	32	6	18.47/ 5.54	Bradonica	1	344- 1376	7.8 - 19.0	50 - 450

2.1.1 Non-technical parameters

Qualitative non-technical data were collected by WP2 partners (Honegger et al, 2024) via literature search as well as expert assessments (through survey and workshop) for key dimensions of nontechnical parameters and were mapped in the form of GIS layers in the WP3. The key dimensions include readiness across social, political (Figure 2-4, Table 2-2), regulatory (Figure 2-5, Figure 2-6, Table 2-3), MRV (Monitoring Reporting and Verification) and Accounting Readiness (Figure 2-7), governmental financial support for CCUS projects (Figure 2-8), Readiness of the CCUS value chain (Figure 2-9), CCUS in marine and land use planning (Figure 2-10) and interaction of CCUS with other decarbonization technologies (Figure 2-11). These data and maps were used for estimation of external nontechnical parameters.

Figure 2-4 Map of public acceptance and political developments in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions

Table 2-2 Public acceptance and political development in the studied regions

Country	Public Acceptance	Political Development
Baltic Sea Region		
Denmark	Medium	Favourable
Estonia	Medium	Business as usual
Finland	Medium	Business as usual
Germany	Low	Business as usual
Latvia	Medium	Business as usual
Lithuania	Low	Unfavourable
Poland	Low	Favourable
Sweden	Medium	Favourable
Mediterranean Sea Region		
France	Low	Favourable
Greece	Low	Business as usual
Italy	Low	Unfavourable
Spain	Medium	Business as usual
Turkey	Medium	Business as usual

Figure 2-5 Map of national CCS regulations in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions.

Table 2-3 International, regional and national CCS regulations in the studied regions

Country	London Protocol	HELCOM	Barcelona Convention	EU CCS Directive	CO ₂ STORAGE
Baltic Sea Region					
Denmark	2019 Provisional Application of Article 6.2	Member	Nm	Implemented	Permitted onshore and offshore
Estonia	Amendment to Article 6 implemented	Member	Nm	Implemented	R&D only
Finland	Amendment to Article 6 implemented	Member	Nm	Implemented	R&D only
Germany	Member of London Protocol	Member	Nm	Implemented	R&D only
Latvia	Nonmember	Member	Nm	Implemented	R&D only
Lithuania	Nonmember	Member	Nm	Implemented	Any CO ₂ injections banned
Poland	Member of London Convention	Member	Nm	Implemented	R&D only
Sweden	2019 Provisional Application of Article 6.2	Member	Nm	Implemented	Permitted only offshore

Country	London Protocol	HELCOM	Barcelona Convention	EU CCS Directive	CO ₂ STORAGE
Mediterranean Sea Region					
France	Member of London Protocol	Nm	Member	Implemented	Permitted onshore and offshore
Greece	Member of London Convention	Nm	Member	Implemented	Excluding selected areas
Italy	Member of London Protocol	Nm	Member	Implemented	Excluding selected areas
Spain	Member of London Protocol	Nm	Member	Implemented	Permitted onshore and offshore
Turkey	Nonmember	Nm	Member	Not applicable	No CCS regulations

Nm – non member

Figure 2-6 Map of international regulations (London Protocol) in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions.

Figure 2-7 Map of MRV and Accounting Readiness in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions

Table 2-4 Monitoring Reporting and Verification (MRV)* and Accounting Readiness** in the Studied Regions

Country	MRV*	Accounting readiness and Carbon Market**
Baltic Sea Region		
Denmark	High	High
Estonia	Low	Low
Finland	Medium	High
Germany	Medium	High
Latvia	Low	Low
Lithuania	Low	Low
Poland	Low	Low
Sweden	Medium	High
Mediterranean Sea Region		
France	Medium	Medium
Greece	Low	Low
Italy	Low	Medium
Spain	Low	Medium
Turkey	Low	Low

*MRV Readiness is an expert judgment based on the following factors:

1) known presence of geological survey companies, 2) known previous participation of key actors in carbon markets, 3) existence of plans for CCS activities.

** Readiness of the national GHG inventory responsible office. Expert judgment based on the following factors:

1) readiness engagement on CCS-related accounting questions, 2) overall quality of previous GHG inventory reports.

Figure 2-8 Map of governmental financial support for CCUS projects in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions.

Figure 2-9 Map of readiness of the CCUS value chain in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions.

Figure 2-10 Map of CCUS in marine and land use planning in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions.

Figure 2-11 Map of interaction of CCUS with other decarbonization technologies in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions

Table 2-5 Business Model, Complexity of the CCUS Value Chain, Interaction with Decarbonisation Technologies and Marine and Land Use Planning in the Studied Regions

	Business model	Complexity of the CCUS value chain	Interaction with other decarbonisation technologies	Marine and land use planning	
Country	Government financial support available for CCS projects	CO ₂ capture, transport and storage infrastructure	CCUS in Industrial Strategy / Plan	CCUS in marine planning	CCUS in land-use planning
Baltic Region					
Denmark	Yes - tailored to individual projects	C, T & S in development	Yes	Yes	Yes - national & regional
Estonia	No	None	No	No	No
Finland	Yes - tailored to individual projects	Capture available	Yes	No	Yes - national & regional
Germany	No	C & T in development	No strategy / plan	No	No
Latvia	No	Capture in development	No strategy / plan	No	No
Lithuania	No	Storage available	No strategy / plan	No	No
Poland	No	C & S in development	No strategy / plan	No	No
Sweden	Yes - tailored to individual projects	C & T available	Yes	No	No
Mediterranean Region					
France	No	C, T & S in development	No	No	Yes - regional
Greece	Yes - tailored to individual projects	T & S in development	Yes	No	No
Italy	Yes - tailored to individual projects	C in development, S available	Yes	No	No
Spain	No	C, T & S available	Yes	No	No
Turkey	No	None	No	No	No

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 SWOT analysis

SWOT analysis is a strategic planning technique used to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to project planning. SWOT analysis of the prospective CCUS cluster projects was applied to technical and non-technical groups of parameters.

Internal group include aspects characterized strengths and weaknesses of the project, while external group include aspects characterising external opportunities and threats (risks) of the project.

For quantification of SWOT analysis, the methodology reported and applied by (Chang & Huang, 2006) could be applied. The Quantified SWOT analytical method applies the concept of Multiple-Attribute Decision Making (MADM), using a multi-layer scheme to simplify complicated problems. As we have to analyse together quantitative and qualitative data, we need statistical methodology. In this report we propose the weights of internal and external factors to be the same. Weights of key factors can be calculated by using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) proposed by Saaty (1980) and applied to SWOT analysis by Chang & Huang (2006).

Figure 2-12 Flowchart of quantified SWOT analysis proposed by (Chang & Huang, 2006)

Internal group (strengths and weaknesses) include aspects of 1) CO₂ emission plants, 2) CO₂ storage sites, 3) available and planned infrastructure, and 4) CO₂ use options.

2.2.2 The most prospective CO₂ use options

To analyse CO₂ use options and to apply the most prospective ones for our CCUS value chains, we prepared the Table 2-6, where the short list of the most promising CCU products is reported based on the recent studies (EC, 2019, Chauvy et al, 2019 and Shokrollahi et al, 2024).

CCU represents an array of technologies leading to different types of products like fuels, chemicals or construction materials. In some of those cases the time that the carbon is stored into the product can vary from short (as in the case of fuels - one year in Table 2-6), to short/medium (as in the case of chemicals and polymers – 10 years), to very long (as in the case of mineralisation products where the CO₂ is permanently bound in the form of carbonates – 50 years in Table 2-6). Accordingly, the climate mitigation effect of the CCU products varies and it depends strongly on the source of CO₂, the energy mix used for their production, the geographical location, the technological maturity of the process, the conventional product that they replace.

In the EC report (EC, 2019) the CCU technologies were analysed including their regulatory aspects. We are discussing here CO₂ use as a feedstock to convert it into value added products such as polymers, minerals, chemicals and synthetic fuels. CCU could offer a promising option for circular economy, industrial innovation and decarbonisation, as well as competitiveness of energy intensive industries. However, policy support is needed to integrate CCU into the CCUS value chains and to bring economic revenues to the large projects. The climate mitigation potential of CCU technologies is dependent on the carbon intensity of the electricity used for the processes, the efficiency of the technologies, the greenhouse gas (GHG) intensity of other inputs, how long the CO₂ stays in its new form, and which products or fuels they replace. Their life cycle analysis can lead to very different results. This report determined 15 the most promising CCU products from the long list of 130: fuels and base chemicals (**ethanol, methane** (biological), **methane** (chemical hydrogenative), **methanol, oxymethylene ether (OME1)**), chemicals (**ethylene; propylene**), intended for the production of polymers (**polyethylene (PE)**), **polyoxymethylene (POM)**, **polypropylene (PP)**, **polycarbonate (BisA-PC)**, **polyols for polyurethane (PU)** foams production) and minerals (**calcium carbonate and sodium carbonate**).

In this study another important conclusion was made, based on LCA. When considering the same product patterns, the **retention time** for carbon in CCU products versus conventional (fossil- or bio-based) products remain the same and thus is **an irrelevant metric for measuring the CO₂ balance**. 2) From a climate mitigation perspective, the benefit of CCU processes depends on the **net GHG emission balance** of the process from cradle-to-gate, for all types of products (minerals, polymers, fuels and chemicals) under the condition that conventional products are replaced.

In the study of Chauvy et al, 2019 the best CO₂ utilization products based on the lower unit price and high market volume were found: **methanol, methane, calcium carbonates, microalgae, sodium carbonates, urea, syngas** and **ethanol**, and compounds that have a high unit price but low market volume, such as **dimethyl carbonates, polycarbonates, formic acid and salicylic acid**.

In the most recent study of Shokrollahi et al, 2024 the extensive statistical analysis of **133** CO₂ utilization pathways were identified from the literature and evaluated using a Multi Criteria Decision Analysis tool, which is based on an Analytic Hierarchy Process, for three different scenarios. These analyses compared 1) technology readiness level, 2) global market size, 3) global market price, 4) CO₂ utilization volume, and 5) CO₂ retention time as screening criteria. Also, three different scenarios, including Economic Vision, Environmental Vision, and Immediate Environmental Action, were considered. The results show that 10 products including **calcium carbonate, ethylene, ethylene oxide, methane, polyethylene, polypropylene, syngas, synthetic fuel, and urea** are the most promising CO₂-based products with respect to the three considered scenarios. As a last step, a general framework was developed to calculate the minimum selling price of the selected CO₂ utilization pathways

to provide comparable economic results. The highest minimum selling prices were associated with **polyethylene and ethylene oxide**.

In the Table 2-6 the urea is excluded from this short list, based on the conclusion from EC, 2019 (high TRL level and available conventional technology). The included nine CO₂-based products include fuels, chemicals and mineral carbonation products with TRL from 6 to 9, market price in the range of 171-1625 Euro, Global market size in the range of 55-8447 Mt.

Table 2-6 Parameters of the most prospective CO₂-based products (Shorollahi et al, 2024 and EC, 2019)

N	CO ₂ conversion method	CO ₂ use product	Global market size, Mt/y	Specific mass t CO ₂ /t product	Total CO ₂ use volume, Mt/y	Product market price (Euro/t)	Retention time, years	TRL
1	Mineral carbonation	Calcium Carbonate, CaCO ₃	125.3	0.439	55.1	309	50	9
2	CO ₂ Hydrogenation	Methane, CH ₄	2300	2.750	6309	171	1	7
3	Dry reforming	Syngas (Synthesis gas, mixture of H ₂ , CO and CO ₂)	968.1	1.292	1251	341	1	8
4	CO ₂ Hydrogenation	Methanol, CH ₃ OH	65.0	1.373	89.3	331	1	8
5	CO ₂ Hydrogenation	Syntetic Liquid fuels (synfuel), (Mixture of CO and H ₂)	2728	3.096	8447	1625	1	6
6	CO ₂ Hydrogenation	Ethylene (C ₂ H ₄)	165.0	3.138	517.8	965	1	8
7	CO ₂ Hydrogenation	Ethylene oxide, (CH ₂ CH ₂ O)	32.3	1.997	64.5	1355	1	9
8	CO ₂ Hydrogenation	Polyethylene(C ₂ H ₄) _n	99.6	3.138	312.5	1107	10	8
9	CO ₂ Hydrogenation	Polypropylene, (C ₃ H ₆) _n	69.1	3.139	216.9	1219	10	8
		Total range	32.3 - 2728	0.439- 3.139	55- 8447	171-1625	1-50	6-9

CCU revenue was excluded from the list of internal parameters for SWOT analysis, considering very uncertain and various CCU production cost, which are reported by different reports and publications.

Figure 2.13 The evolution of the e-SAF cost based on the electricity price (Skypower, 2024).

According to a recent study by the Skypower Project (Skypower, 2024), the levelised cost of production of unsubsidized e-SAF production in Europe by 2030 would span from 5000-8000 €/t, approximately 5-8 times higher than the price of fossil jet fuel. Up to 45% of this amount is related to the price of renewable electricity and up to 60% corresponds to the CAPEX of the electrolyser and the fuel synthesis installation. The Figure 2.13 shows the evolution of the e-SAF cost based on the electricity price.

H₂ and CO₂ are considered as two of the main contributors of the costs of e-methanol and estimates that these costs can decrease to levels as low as 250 \$/t by 2050 (IRENA AND METHANOL INSTITUTE, 2021).

Scientific literature shows a rather wide spectrum in cost evaluation for e-methanol and e-SAF mainly due to the difference in the underlying assumptions. Sollai et al. (2023) have calculated a levelized cost for the production of methanol (LCoM) from industrial CO₂ of about 960€/t, around double the current market price for fossil-derived methanol; they have also estimated the correlation between LCoM, electricity costs and hours of operation (Figure 2.14).

Figure 2.14. A levelized cost for the production of methanol (LCoM) variation with plant operation and electricity cost (Sollai et al., 2023).

A base minimum selling price (equivalent to the levelised cost of production) of an e-SAF based on atmospheric CO₂ was estimated at about 6200 €/t, highly sensitive on electricity prices and DAC costs. Increasing production capacities of Power-to-Liquid systems will according to the writers lead to cost reductions as scaling up a DAC PtL system is not limited by feedstock supply and has less location restrictions (Rojas-Michaga et al., 2023).

3 CO₂ value chains in two regions

3.1 Baltic - 1: Latvian - Lithuanian onshore CCUS project

The Baltic-1 onshore cluster includes four of the largest Latvian CO₂ emitters and two Lithuanian plants located close to the Latvian - Lithuanian border (Orlen refinery and Akmenes cement plant, owned by Schwenk). This cluster will store annually 3.1 Mt CO₂ from three plants (Latvian and Lithuanian Schwenk-owned cement plants and Orlen Refinery) in the onshore North Blidene and Blidene structures. Latvian two Latvenergo PP and one Rigas Siltums TP located in the Riga region will transport about 0.95 Mt CO₂ in the Dobeles storage site in western Latvia using up to 150 km CO₂ pipelines (Shogenova et al, 2023).

Figure 3.1. Map of the Baltic-1 scenario with pipeline routes modelled along natural gas pipelines corridors. Latvian Riga cluster of three power plants will transport CO₂ to Dobeles structure. Cement plants from Latvia and Lithuania and Orlen Lithuania will transport CO₂ to North-Blidene structure in Latvia. Blidene structure is proposed for hydrogen storage.

For onshore cluster CO₂ use for geothermal energy recovery could be applied in the region of central Latvian geothermal anomaly, reaching 62°C in Pape 23 well at the west-south coast of Latvia and 55°C in Vircava-5 well, located about 35-40 km from the Dobeles structure by road. All countries are planning to produce hydrogen. They can store it in the in the Blidene structure onshore (Figures 1-3).

Table 3-1 Parameters of the Baltic 1 value chain

Cluster ID	Involved countries	Total CO2 emissions, Mt/y	Emission sources	Emission clusters	Storage sites	Number of storage sites	Total capacity, Mt	Distance from emissions to storage, km	Emission clusters per country	Storage sites per cluster
<u>Baltic 1</u>	Latvia Lithuania	4.25	6	3	Onshore North-Blidene Blidene Dobele	3	403	10-145	1.5	1.5

3.1.1 CO₂ emission clusters

Table 3-2 Clusters of CO₂ emissions of Baltic 1 value chain

Cluster ID	CO2 cluster	Country	Emitter ID	Facility name	City/Region	Industry sector	CO2 emissions Mt/y	Planning CO2 use	Planning H2 production	Starting Year	CCUS ZEN networking Partner
Baltic 1	1	Latvia	LVA_12 4056	Schwenk Latvija	Broceni	Cement	0.75	Yes		2030	Yes
Baltic 1	1	Lithuania	LTU_18	Orlen Lietuva	Telšiai	Refinery	1.5	Fossil CO2	Blue H2	2030	Yes
Baltic 1	1	Lithuania	LTU_15	Akmenės Cement	Šiauliai	Cement	1.0	Yes		2030	Yes
					TOTAL	For cluster 1	3.25				
Baltic 1	2	Latvia	LVA_10 563	Latvenergo Tec-2	Riga	Power, Natural gas	0.68	Yes	Blue H2	2030	Yes
Baltic 1	2	Latvia	LVA_10 350	Latvenergo Tec-1	Riga	Power, Natural gas	0.227				Yes
Baltic 1	2	Latvia	LVA_85 85	Rigas Siltums TP	Riga	Power, Natural gas	0.1				
					TOTAL For cluster 2		1.0				
					TOTAL for Baltic-1		4.25				

3.1.2 CO₂ storage sites and CO₂ transport in the Baltic-1

Table 3-3 Properties of CO₂ storage sites in the Baltic 1 value chain (a)

Country	Storage site ID	Storage type	Storage unit	Daughter Unit	Lithology	Area, km ²	Net to gross ratio	Depth Top, m	Thickness, m	Porosity, decimal	Permeability, mD	Temperature, °C	Pressure, MPa	CO ₂ density, kg/m ³
Latvia	S_LV4	DSA	Cambrian Wulian Deimena Formation (CWDF)	Dobele	Sandstone	70	0.85	950	52	0.19	360	18	13	900
Latvia	S_LV2	DSA	CWDF	Blidene	Sandstone	62	0.8	1168	66	0.21	860	22.9	126.5	866
Latvia	S_LV10	DSA	CWDF	North Blidene	Sandstone	141	0.75	1035	48	0.2	370	18	110	881
					Average		0.8			0.2	530			

Table 3-4 Properties of CO₂ storage sites in the Baltic 1 value chain (b)

Daughter Unit	Primary seal	Primary seal_lithology	Primary seal_thickness	Secondary_seals	Boundary_condition	Seff	SRL	Seismic_survey	Capacity_mean	Wells	Abandoned_wells	Modeling	Baseline_data
Dobele	Lower Ordovician	Claystone	59	Ordovician and Silurian	Semi-closed	20	4	2D	106	22	16	+	+
Blidene	Lower Ordovician	Claystone	44.5	Ordovician and Silurian	Closed	5	3	2D	29.6	1	1	+	-
North Blidene	Lower Ordovician	Claystone	42.6	Middle and Upper Ordovician and Silurian	Semi-closed	30	3	2D	267	4	4	+	-
	Average		48.7			18.3	3.3	Total	403	27	21		

Table 3-5 Pipelines distance to the storage sites

Country	Emitter ID	Facility name	City/Region	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions Mt/y	Storage site	Pipelines' segment	Pipeline length (km)
Latvia	LVA_124056	Schwenk Latvija	Broceni	Cement	0.75	North Blidene	Schwenk - North Blidene	10
Lithuania	LTU_18	Orlen Lietuva	Telšiai	Refinery	1.5	North Blidene	Orlen - North Blidene	63
Lithuania	LTU_15	Akmenės Cement	Šiauliai	Cement	1	North Blidene	Akmenes - North Blidene	50
		TOTAL for cluster 1			3.25			123
Latvia	LVA_10563	Latvenergo Tec-2	Riga	Power, natural gas	0.68	Dobele	Tec-2 - Dobele	130
Latvia	LVA_10350	Latvenergo Tec-1	Riga	Power, natural gas	0.227	Dobele	Tec-1 - Hub I	9.5
Latvia	LVA_8585	Rigas Siltums TP	Riga	Power, natural gas	0.1	Dobele	Siltums - Hub I	6
							Hub I - Hub II	14.5
		TOTAL for cluster 2			1			160
			TOTAL		4.25			283

3.1.3 CO₂ use options in the Baltic-1

41% of CO₂ emissions in Baltic-1 clusters are coming from the cement industry. After water, concrete is the most widely used material on earth. Approximately 4.3 billion tons of cement — the principal ingredient in concrete — were produced in 2021. However, production of cement is also responsible for around 7% of annual global CO₂ emissions. Main CO₂ valorisation pathway is mineralisation. Carbon Cure technology for the concrete industry, introduces recycled CO₂ into fresh concrete to reduce its carbon footprint without compromising performance. Once injected, the CO₂ undergoes a mineralisation process and becomes permanently embedded. Different technological approaches are available worldwide, but stakeholders did not clearly describe their strategy regarding CO₂ use.

Lithuanian Minister of Transport and Communications Marius Skuodis announced at the International Conference E-fuels in Berlin in June 2024 that Lithuania could also become a significant player in the production and transport of green fuels in Europe having the needed facilities and know-how for producing e-fuels at Orlen company. Lithuania considered its potential to become a future green energy hub in the Baltic region thanks to offshore winds what will generate green electricity on a 100-ha site. The surplus of green energy will be exported abroad (LRV.LT, 2024).

For the Baltic-1 scenario we assume that 95% of CO₂ emissions will be captured, from which 10% of emissions will be used. Using these assumptions, 4.04 Mt/y of CO₂ will be captured and 0.4 Mt used (Table 3-6).

Table 3-6. CO₂ captured and utilised in the Baltic-1 project

Country	Cluster Location - City/Region	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions produced Mt/y	Number of emitters	CO ₂ emissions captured, Mt/y	CO ₂ emissions used, Mt/y
Latvia Lithuania	Broceni, Telsiai Šiauliai	Cement, Refinery	3.25	3	3.09	0.31
Latvia	Riga	Power, Natural Gas	1.0	3	0.95	0.10
			4.25	6	4.04	0.40

3.1.4 Main advantages

The main advantages of the proposed project is close location to the onshore storage sites, very good reservoir properties of Cambrian Deimena Formation reservoir sandstones, explained by low temperatures, high CO₂ density and therefore large storage capacity, high storage readiness level and readiness of the main industrial stakeholders to develop CCS projects (Schwenk Latvija, Latvenergo and Orlen).

3.1.5 Main challenges

The main challenges of the proposed project are non-technical, including regulatory and social, considering that storage sites land is owned by local landlords, and CO₂ storage ban is not yet raised. Governmental financial support from Latvia and Lithuania are not yet envisaged.

3.2 Baltic - 2: Danish, Swedish and German CCUS onshore and offshore project

The Baltic-2 combined on-/off-shore cluster has 8 storage sites available. The two offshore sites are under development by commercial parties. An exploration license has been issued for the onshore Gassum site to Wintershall Dea International GmbH & INEOS E&P A/S.

The Baltic-2 CCUS project includes nine clusters of 33 emitters divided in two development phases from three countries (Denmark, Sweden and Germany) with an annual CO₂ emissions volume of 22.7 Mt and respective captured CO₂ volume of 20.1 Mt, from which up to 6.1 Mt will be directed for utilisation (CCU). The project is planned for 30 years of CO₂ storage in six DSA (deep saline aquifers), and for 20 years of CO₂ storage in two DOGFs. All CO₂ captured in the Bremen cluster will be utilised in a CCU sub-value chain. Emissions captured in the Gothenburg cluster which are not utilised, are sent to offshore geological storage sites in Denmark (Inez and Lisa sites). From Esbjerg, a ship with CO₂ from the remaining German industrial clusters and the Fredericia and Esbjerg clusters is sent to Greensand and Inez sites. All CO₂ that cannot be shipped from these clusters or that is captured from the remaining

clusters is sent to a pipeline network. Using pipeline network, the CO₂ not used in a CCU installation in Aalborg is distributed to the geological storage sites Bifrost, Jammerbugt, Gassum, Voldum and Thorning (Shogenova et al, 2024).

Table 3-7 Parameters of the Baltic 2 value chain

Cluster ID	Involved countries	Total CO ₂ emissions, Mt/y	Emmission sources	Emission clusters	Storage sites	Number of storage sites	Total capacity, Mt	Distance from emissions to storage, km	Emission clusters per country	Storage sites per cluster
Baltic-2	Germany Denmark Sweden	22.66	33	9	Gassum, Voldum, Jammerbugt Inez, Bifrost, Greensand, Lisa, Thorning	8	928	5-750	3	0.9

3.2.1 CO₂ emission clusters

Figure 3.2 Overview map of Baltic-2, with CO₂ storage onshore, nearshore and offshore. A pipeline re-use is suggested for one of the offshore storage sites. For the other off- and near-shore sites, ship transport is assumed. Map from Deliverable D3.1.

In its preliminary form, as detailed in Deliverable 1.2 (Gravaud et al., 2023), the Baltic-2 project included eight different emission clusters, including 37 emitters from the three participating countries, which collectively emit approximately 42.6 Mt of CO₂ annually. The reporting of the clusters carried out in Deliverable D3.1, however, has modified the list based on additional technical and commercial examinations.

Nine emission clusters were identified with up to 33 individual emission sources in total, resulting in 22.7 Mt annual maximum emissions and captured maximum amount nearing 20.1 Mt. For the present analysis, the minimum estimates in Deliverable 1.2 (Gravaud et al., 2024) for emissions are selected. The industry designation is summarised from Deliverable D3.1 (Shogenova et al. 2024). The results are shown in Table 3-8.

Table 3-8 Clusters of CO₂ emissions of Baltic 2 value chain

Cluster ID	Country	CO ₂ emissions Mt/y (min-max)	Industry	Number of emitters (min-max)	Planning CO ₂ use
Bremen Cluster	Germany	2.78–3.43	Power	2–3	?
Hannover Cluster	Germany	3.12–3.99	Power, cement	4–5	Y
Hamburg Cluster	Germany	1.05–3.80	Power, cement	1–4	Y
Gothenburg Cluster	Sweden	3.12–4.12	Refinery, chemical, waste, power	5–9	Y
Aalborg Cluster	Denmark	2.48–2.48	Cement, power	2–2	Y
Aarhus Cluster	Denmark	0.82–2.72	Power	2–3	?
West Midtjylland Cluster	Denmark	0.00–0.62	Power, waste	0–2	?
Fredericia Cluster	Denmark	0.85–1.28	Power, refinery	3–4	Y
Esbjerg Emitter	Denmark	0.22	Power, waste	1	?
Total		14.44–22.66		20–33	

3.2.2 CO₂ storage sites and CO₂ transport in the Baltic-2

Table 3-9 Properties of CO₂ storage sites in Denmark in the Baltic-2 value chain (a)

Storage site name	Storage type	Storage unit	Lithology	Area, km ²	Net to gross ratio	Depth Top, m	Thickness, m	Porosity, %	Permeability, mD	Temperature, °C	Pressure, MpA	CO ₂ density, kg/m ³
Gassum	DSA	Gassum Fm	Sandstone	233	80	1364	130	25	461	40	14	750
Voldum	DSA	Gassum Fm	Sandstone	560	80	1700	128	25	464	50	18	750
Jammerbu gt	DSA	Gassum Fm	Sandstone	140	80	1880	120	25	400	55	19	730
Inez	DSA	Gassum Fm	Sandstone	250	80	1660	120	25	400	45	17	770
Bifrost	DOGF	Jurassic	Sandstone	16	80	3475	100	20	200	90	36	760

D.3.3 A generic framework for selection of the most promising CCUS value chains

Greensand	DOGF	Paleocene	Sandstone	16	80	1650	100	25	600	45	17	770
Lisa	DSA	Gassum Fm	Sandstone	70	80	1720	120	25	400	50	18	750
Thorning	DSA	Gassum Fm	Sandstone	210	80	1500	130	18	109	45	16	750

Table 3-10 Properties of CO₂ storage sites in the Baltic 2 value chain (b)

Storage site	Seal	Seal lithology	Seal Thickness	Secondary_seals	Boundary_condition	Seff	Capacity_mean	SRL	Seismic_survey	Wells	Abandoned wells	Modeling	Baseline_data
Gassum	Lower Jurassic	Claystone	150	Cretaceous	Open	10	146	2	2D	1	1	-	-
Voldum	Lower Jurassic	Claystone	150	Cretaceous	Open	10	213	2	2D	1	1	-	-
Jammerbugt	Lower Jurassic	Claystone	150	Cretaceous	Open	10	100	2	2D	0		-	-
Inez	Lower Jurassic	Claystone	150	Cretaceous	Open	10	178	2	2D	1	1	-	-
Bifrost	Lower Jurassic	Claystone	150	Cretaceous	Open	10	60	6	3D	5	3	+	-
Greensand	Lower Jurassic	Claystone	150	Cretaceous	Open	10	128	6	3D	10		+	-
Lisa	Lower Jurassic	Claystone	150	Cretaceous	Open	10	29	2	2D	0		-	-
Thorning	Lower Jurassic	Claystone	150	Cretaceous	Open	10	74	2	2D	0		-	-
				Total			928	2-6		18			

3.2.3 CO₂ transport options in the Baltic-2 project

The transport infrastructure solutions presented in Deliverable D3.1 (Shogenova et al. 2024) considers that all CO₂ captured in the Bremen cluster is utilised in a CCU sub-value chain. Emissions captured in the Gothenburg cluster which are not utilised in a local CCU infrastructure, are sent to offshore geological storage sites in Denmark (Inez and Lisa). From Esbjerg, a ship with CO₂ from Germany, Fredericia and Esbjerg is sent to Greensand and Inez. All CO₂ that cannot be shipped from these clusters or that is captured from the remaining clusters is sent to a pipeline network. Within the pipeline network, the CO₂ not used in a CCU installation in Aalborg is distributed to the geological storage sites Bifrost, Jammerbugt, Gassum, Voldum and Thorning.

Examples of pipeline routes have been listed in Deliverable D3.1 (Shogenova et al. 2025) and a few selected for the Baltic-2 cluster are presented here in Table 3-11.

Table 3-11 Pipeline list for the selected scenario

Pipe #	From	To	Cluster	Country	Phase	State	Flowrate, t/h	Length, km	Size, in
P18	Intersection Esbjerg	Bifrost	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	100	256	14

P23	Intersection close to S_DK_18	Intersection west Gassum	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	751	81	24
P24	Intersection west Gassum	Gassum	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	463	37	18

The assumption presented in Deliverable D3.1 (Shogenova et al. 2024) is that CO₂ from the Gothenburg and Esbjerg clusters will be shipped to offshore storage locations in Denmark. The respective ship cycle times are presented in Table 3-12.

Table 3-12 Cycle times from selected harbours to offshore storage sites

From	To	Distance, km	Cycle time, h
Gothenburg	Lisa	210	54
Gothenburg	Inez	330	65
Esbjerg	Inez	215	54
Esbjerg	Greensand	255	58

The selected scenario for transportation infrastructure is a concept out of many possible. The current selection is not equivalent to a thorough analysis and comparison between the different transportation solution. Nonetheless, it takes inspiration in existing or planned projects and provides a pragmatic solution for implementing a CCUS network in the three countries analysed.

3.2.4 CO₂ use options in the Baltic-2

Two CO₂ utilization pathways (near emitters or near intermediate hubs) were explored within this region, converting CO₂ into methanol or synthetic jet fuel, as described in Deliverable D3.1 (Shogenova et al. 2024). Nevertheless, The Swedish FlagshipONE e-methanol project under development, considered as the “largest e-Methanol project under construction in Europe” was recently scrapped by Orsted (August 2024) and possible offtakes are not identified yet. Most shipping firms remained reluctant in committing to long-term procurement contracts for methanol produced via sustainable means and the project was challenged by higher energy, equipment and capex costs. This may reveal the immaturity of the regulatory system and measures in place currently struggle to bridge the price gaps between fossil and synthetic marine fuels (S&P Global, 2024).

In Denmark and Germany, there are still active projects for CO₂utilization. Power-to-Liquid plant at H&R's Hamburg from Power-to-Liquid synthesis technology, developed by Karlsruhe-based technology company INERATEC, will in future produce around 200 tons of e-Fuels for road as well as rail transport and around 150 tons of e-Waxes for use in the cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and food industries (P2XEurope (2022).

Recently 30 CCU projects with total budget of about 0.83 M DKK in various stages of research and development were reported in Denmark (INNO-CCUS, 2023)

Using the same methodology and assumptions than explained in D3.1, 20.14 Mt/y of CO₂ will be captured in Baltic-2, including 8.06 Mt of bio-CO₂. It is also assumed that 6.05 Mt of captured biogenic CO₂ will go to utilization. A full overview by cluster is shown in table 3-13, with total captured emission and utilized, including two options, methanol and synthetic jet fuel. Average capture capacity per installation in every country is also estimated for the Baltic-2.

Table 3-13 Overview of possible CO₂ for capture and utilisation for Baltic-2 (Shogenova et al, 2024, D3.1)

Country	Cluster acting as collection hub	Total captured CO ₂ from all emitters, Mt/y	Captured Biogenic CO ₂ (Included in total), Mt/y	Captured CO ₂ from all emitters for CCU, Mt/y	Number of CCU installations close to the collection hub	Average capture capacity of CCU installation, Mt/y	Average product capacity of CCU installation, Mt/y	
							Methanol	Synthetic jet fuel
Germany	Bremen	10.66	5.59	3.2	5	0.64	0.45	0.192
Denmark	Aalborg	5.53	1.82	1.66	5	0.332	0.232	0.100
Sweden	Gothenburg	3.95	0.65	1.19	5	0.238	0.167	0.072
Total for Baltic-2		20.14	8.06	6.05	15	0.24-0.64	4.25	1.82

3.2.5 Main advantages

The proposed value chain promotes cross-border cooperation for 9 industrial clusters from three countries and translates potential investment possibilities being studied today by multiple parties.

The Baltic-2 cluster include 8 storage sites in Denmark with very good reservoir properties, large thickness of primary cap rocks, high storage capacity about 1Gt CO₂ and has various options to transport CO₂ from 9 emission clusters in three countries to 8 storage sites located onshore, nearshore and offshore and represented by DOGFs and DSAs. CO₂ capture and CO₂ use options are under development and many CCUS research and demo projects are ongoing in Denmark.

The favourable CCS policies and regulations and financial governmental support in Denmark, where CO₂ storage sites are located and implemented international regulations in Denmark and Sweden are additional advantages.

3.2.6 Main challenges

The main challenge for this project is connected with international regulations. From three participating countries, Germany did not implement an amendment to the article 6 of London Protocol and did not send the provisional application to IMO. However, according to EU CCS Directive, bilateral agreement between two participating countries (CO₂ emitting and storing)

can be the same legal basis as London Protocol provisions, needed for export of CO₂ for geological storage under the seabed.

3.3 Baltic - 3: Danish, Swedish and German CCUS onshore and nearshore project

The Baltic-3 project is a cross-border value chain with 5.9 Mt of CO₂ emissions produced by 16 plants from Denmark, Sweden and Germany and three storage sites (Havnsø, Stenlille and Rødby) onshore and nearshore Denmark in Zealand and Lolland. The total average storage capacity is about 224 Mt CO₂. The distance from CO₂ clusters to storage sites is from 5 up to 200 km, the total estimated transport distance is 460 km.

Figure 3.3 Baltic-3 project (Copenhagen hub value chain in D1.2). Dots surrounded by red polygons represent emission clusters. Orange forms represent onshore/nearshore storage sites. Yellow and brown lines represent shipping and pipeline transportation, respectively.

Two CO₂ emission clusters in Denmark (Copenhagen and North-western Zealand) produced in 2021 about 1.9 Mt CO₂, South Sweden cluster produced 1.5 Mt CO₂ and Rostock cluster produced 2.5 Mt CO₂.

The Baltic-3 combined onshore cluster has 3 storage sites available. Exploration licenses have been issued for the onshore Havnsø site (Equinor Low Carbon Solutions Denmark A/S & Ørsted Carbon Solutions A/S) and for the Rødby storage site (Carboncuts A/S).

Table 3-14 Parameters of the Baltic 3 value chain

Involved countries	Total CO2 emissions, Mt/y	Emission sources	Emission clusters	Storage sites	Number of storage sites	Total capacity, Mt	Distance from emissions to storage, km	Emission clusters per country	Storage sites per cluster
Germany Denmark Sweden	5.9	16	4	Onshore - Rødby, Havnsø, Stenlille	3	224	5-115	1.3	0.75

3.3.1 CO₂ emission clusters

Table 3-15 Clusters of CO₂ emissions of Baltic 3 value chain.

CO ₂ cluster	Country	City/Region	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions Mt/y	Number of emitters	Planning CO ₂ use	Starting Year
1	Germany	Rostock	Cement	2.52	3	?	2030
2	Denmark	Copenhagen	WTE	1.36	6	Y	2030
3	Denmark	NW Zealand	Cement	0.53	1	?	2030
4	Sweden	South Sweden	Power, Natural gas	1.50	6	Y	2030
			Total	5.91	16		

3.3.2 CO₂ storage sites in Denmark and CO₂ transport in the Baltic-3

Table 3-16 Properties of CO₂ storage sites in the Baltic 3 value chain (a)

Storage type	Storage site	Daughter Unit	Lithology	Area, km ²	Net to gross ratio	Depth Top, m	Thickness, m	Porosity	Permeability, mD	Temperature, °C	Pressure, MPa	CO ₂ density, kg/m ³
DSA	Stenlille	Gassum	Sandstone	24	0.8	1460	150	0.25	600	42	16	770
DSA	Havnsø	Gassum	Sandstone	119	0.46	1375	200	0.22	260	40	16	790
DSA	Rødby	Bunter	Sandstone	138	0.24	1075	256	0.24	385	35	15	810
		Average		94	0.50	1303	202	0	415	39	16	790

Table 3-17 Properties of CO₂ storage sites in the Baltic 3 value chain (b)

Daughter Unit	Seal	Seal_lithology	Seal_thickness	Secondary_seals	Boundary_condition	Seff	Capacity_mean	SRL	Seismic_survey	Wells	Abandoned_wells	Modeling	Baseline_data
Gassum	Jurassic	Claystone	150	Cretaceous	Open	0.1	36	3	3D	19		+	+
Gassum	Jurassic	Claystone	150	Cretaceous	Open	0.1	76	2	2D	0		+	-

Bunter	Juras- sic	Clay- stone	150	Cretace- ous	Ope- n	0.1	112	2	2D	2	2	+	-
Average			150	Total			224			21	2		

The estimated storage capacities have been modified compared to early reports due to a new evaluation of the storage efficiency coefficient, lowering this from 0.40 to 0.10.

3.3.3 CO₂ transport options in the Baltic-3

For CO₂ transportation, the value chain needs a pipeline network connecting the three storage sites with clusters. For the Rostock cluster in Germany, shipping line in the value chain, during the initial stage would transport the CO₂ to the Rødby storage site. On a further stage, a pipeline could transport the CO₂ from the Rostock cluster to any of the three storage sites selected.

The Copenhagen cluster can serve as an import hub of CO₂ from other clusters, connecting South Sweden cluster by pipeline. This value chain segment has been studied in multiple projects such as the C4 – Carbon Capture Cluster Copenhagen for the storage sites of Stenlille and Havnsø.

The North-western Zealand cluster, presented by only one emitter, represents the possibility of an import hub to collect CO₂ from multiple cross-border locations by ship and send it to the Havnsø storage site.

3.3.4 CO₂ use options in the Baltic-3

“Green Fuels for Denmark” is an IPCEI supported project in the area of Copenhagen. The latest news of September 2024 about this project is that the main partner Ørsted has announced a suspension of the project. Green Fuels for Denmark was a flagship project for the production of green fuels and was the first gigawatt-scale hydrogen plant to be conceived in the world. The project was launched May 2020 with Copenhagen Airport, A. P. Møller-Mærsk, DSV, DFDS, SAS and Ørsted as partners. Unfortunately, now put on hold.

Baltic-3 project produced 4.55 Mt CO₂ from cement an energy industry, 1.36 Mt from W-t-E industry and in total 5.91 Mt. From this amount 5.62 Mt could be captured and 0.56 Mt used (Table 3-18).

Table 3-18 Overview of possible CO₂ for capture and utilization for Baltic-3

Country	Cluster Location - City/Region	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions produced Mt/y	Number of emitters	CO ₂ emissions captured, Mt/y	CO ₂ emissions used, Mt/y
Germany	Rostock	Cement	2.52	3	2.39	0.24
Denmark	Copenhagen	WtE	1.36	6	1.29	0.13
Denmark	NW Zealand	Cement	0.53	1	0.50	0.05
Sweden	South Sweden	Power, Natural gas	1.5	6	1.43	0.14
		Total	5.91	16	5.62	0.56

3.3.5 Main advantages

The proposed value chain promotes cross-border cooperation for three countries and translates potential investment possibilities being studied today by multiple parties.

The Copenhagen cluster shows also interesting potential for the CCU applications with the (now suspended) Lighthouse project of Green fuels for Denmark receiving IPCEI funding, or the Vordingborg port project for the production of CCU fuels from captured CO₂ and renewable hydrogen.

3.3.6 Main challenges

The main challenge for this project could be the same as for the Baltic-2 project, connected with international regulations. From three participating countries, Germany did not implement an amendment to the article 6 of London Protocol and did not send the provisional application to IMO. However, according to EU CCS Directive, bilateral agreement between two participating countries (CO₂ emitting and storing) can be the same legal basis as London Protocol provisions, needed for export of CO₂ for geological storage under the seabed.

3.4 Baltic-4: Northern Poland CCUS onshore project

The value chain includes southern cluster of Northern Poland region studied in D1.2, the Kuyavia-Masovia cluster Figure 3.4. There are 18 emitters within the cluster, 11 in case of old coal fired energy installations are disregarded. These 11 emitters selected make 8.19 Mt CO₂ per year Table 3-20 to be captured then stored or used. Two saline aquifer structures (Konary and Kamionki) located nearby the four emitter subclusters are proposed as storage sites, where CO₂ can be delivered by pipelines of length 4.2-38.2 km, connecting the emission subclusters and storage sites.

Figure 3.4 Map of the Baltic-4 scenario with pipeline routes modelled using (where possible) natural gas pipelines corridors.

3.4.1 CO₂ emission sources in the Baltic-4

Table 3-19 Parameters of the Baltic-4 value chain

Involved countries	Total CO ₂ emissions, Mt/y	Emission sources	Emission clusters	Storage sites, onshore	Number of storage sites	Total capacity, Mt	Distance from emissions to storage, km	Emission clusters per country	Storage sites per cluster
Poland	8.19	11	4	Konary (S_PL24), Kamionki (S_PL22)	2	381	4.2-38.2	4	0.4

Table 3-20 Clusters of CO₂ emissions of Baltic 4 value chain

CO ₂ cluster	Emitter ID	Facility name	City/Region	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions Mt/y	Planning CO ₂ use	Planning H ₂ production	Starting Year	CCUS ZEN networking Partner
1	E_PL_43	Bydgoszcz WtE	Bydgoszcz	Energy from waste	0.164	No		2030	No
			Total for cluster 1		0.164				
2	E_PL_3	LaFarge Cement Piechcin Bielawy	Piechcin-Bielawy	Cement	1.266	No		2028	Parent company Holcim
2	E_PL_65	Piechcin lime	Piechcin	Other - Lime	0.196	No		2030	No
2	E_PL_27	Janikowo chemicals	Janikowo	Chemicals (other)	0.179	No		2030	No
2	E_PL_27	Inowrocław chemicals	Inowrocław	Chemicals (other)	0.241	No		2030	No
			Total for cluster 2		1.882	No			
3	E_PL_17	Włocławek NGCC	Włocławek	Power (CHP), Natural gas	1.022	No		2030	No
3	E_PL_1	Włocławek ammonia	Włocławek	Ammonia	0.791	Yes	blue then green	2030	No
			Total for cluster 3		1.813				
4	E_PL_193	Płock refiner	Płock	Refineries	2.557	Yes	blue then green	2030	No
4	E_PL_21	Płock chemicals	Płock	Chemicals (other)	0.721	Yes	blue then green	2030	No

4	E_PL_22	Płock chemicals	Płock	Chemicals (other)	0.103	Yes	blue then green	2030	No
4	E_PL_177	Płock NGCC	Płock	Power (CHP), Natural gas	0.947	No		2030	No
Total for cluster 4					4.328				
Total for Baltic-4					8.187				

Bydgoszcz subcluster includes one small energy from waste plant, Piechcin-Janikowo-Inowrocław subcluster includes cement (the biggest emitter in the subcluster, owned by Holcim-Lafarge), lime and chemical plants (owned by CIECH), and Włocławek subcluster – an ammonia and a CCS-ready gas fired power plant of Orlen. Płock subcluster, of the biggest emission share in the value chain, includes an oil refinery (the biggest emitter there), chemical plants and a CCS-ready gas fired power plant of Orlen.

3.4.2 CO₂ storage sites and CO₂ transport in the Baltic-4

Table 3-21 Properties of CO₂ storage sites in the Baltic 4 value chain (a)

Storage site ID	Storage type	Storage unit	Daughter Unit	Lithology	Area, km ²	Depth Top, m	Thickness, m	Porosity, %	Permeability, mD	Temperature, °C	Pressure, MPa	CO ₂ density, kg/m ³
S_P L24	DSA	Lower Jurassic to lower-most Middle Jurassic	multiple: Borucice, Drzewica, Gielniów, Ostrowiec	Sandstone	250	847	160	15	300	41	8.6	392
S_P L22	DSA	Lower Cretaceous	Mogilno	Sandstone	75	1285	80	20	400	42	12.7	689

Table 3-22 Properties of CO₂ storage sites in the Baltic 4 value chain (b)

Daughter Unit	Seal	Seal lithology	Seal thickness, m	Secondary seals	Boundary condition	Seff, %	Capacity mean	SRL	Seismic survey	Wells	Abandoned wells	Modeling	Baseline data	
multiple: Borucice, Drzewica, Gielniów, Ostrowiec	Lower Bajocian	Claystone, Mudstone	71		Bathonian	Closed	20	282	2	2D	3	3	-	-
Mogilno	Upper Cretaceous	Marl, marly limestone	250		Cretaceous	Closed	20	99	2	2D	3	3	-	-

Concerning storage options

Table 3-22, the multi-reservoir Jurassic saline aquifer structure Konary is proposed as a storage site of three subclusters located W, NW and E of the structure Figure 3.4. Another storage site is the double-reservoir saline aquifer structure Kamionki (Lower Cretaceous

reservoir was selected in the scenario, but there is there is also a deeper Jurassic reservoir as a possible backup) located very close to Płock emitter subcluster. These structures have likely a sufficient storage capacity, enabling possible enlargement of the value chain, but they are explored by old 2-D seismic and a couple of wells only, so to develop the storage sites detailed exploration programs are needed.

The shortest proposed pipeline route is between Płock subcluster and Kamionki storage site – 4.2 km Table 3-23 and the longest – between Bydgoszcz energy from waste plant to Konary storage site (38.2 km). The second longest pipeline route (35.8 km) collects emissions of Piechcin-Janikowo-Inowroćła emission subcluster as well as the Bydgoszcz plant.

Table 3-23 Pipelines distance to the storage sites in the Baltic-4

Emitter ID	Facility name	City/Region	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions, Mt/y	Storage site	Pipelines' segment	Pipelines length, km
E_PL_43	Bydgoszcz WtE	Bydgoszcz	Energy from waste	0.164	Konary	Bydgoszcz – Hub (Inowroćław)	38.2
TOTAL for cluster 1				0.164			38.2
E_PL_3	LaFarge Cement Piechcin Bielawy	Piechcin-Bielawy	Cement	1.266	Konary	Piechcin-Bielawy – Piechcin	1.5
E_PL_65	Piechcin lime	Piechcin	Other - Lime	0.196	Konary	Piechcin – Janikowo	7.7
E_PL_27	Janikowo chemicals	Janikowo	Chemicals (other)	0.179	Konary	Janikowo - Hub (Inowroćław)	9.9
E_PL_27	Inowroćław chemicals	Inowroćław	Chemicals (other)	0.241	Konary	Hub (Inowroćław) – Konary	16.7
TOTAL for cluster 2				1.882			35.8
E_PL_117	Włocławek NGCC	Włocławek	Power (CHP), Natural gas	1.022	Konary	Włocławek (power plant) – Włocławek (ammonia plant)	2.8
E_PL_1	Włocławek ammonia	Włocławek	Ammonia	0.791	Konary	Włocławek – Konary	27.0
TOTAL for cluster 3				1.813			29.8
E_PL_193	Płock refiner	Płock	Refineries	2.557	Kamionki	Płock (refinery) – Płock (power plant)	0.7

						& chemicals)	
E_PL_21	Plock chemicals	Plock	Chemicals (other)	0.721	Kamionki	Plock – Kamionki	3.5
E_PL_22	Plock chemicals	Plock	Chemicals (other)	0.103	Kamionki		
E_PL_177	Plock NGCC	Plock	Power (CHP), Natural gas	0.947	Kamionki		
TOTAL for cluster 4				4.328			4.2
TOTAL for Baltic-4 scenario				8.187			108.0

3.4.3 CO₂ use options in the Baltic-4

There is no particular published information on the stakeholder plans on CO₂ use in case of emitters within the value chain. However, in petrochemical and chemical installations of Orlen in Plock and Wloclawek subclusters blue hydrogen is (or to be) produced and as a byproduct of chemical processes relatively pure CO₂ stream is obtained, so a part of captured stream can be used to produce various goods. Another possibility includes the use of CO₂ in cement industry – in Holcim-Lafarge cement plant of this value chain the capture unit is to be commissioned in a few years, so a part of the captured stream could be used in concrete production.

In the Baltic-4 scenario in Poland 8.19 Mt/y of CO₂ is produced by 11 emitters from 4 clusters, 7.78 Mt captured, and 0.78 Mt used. Emitters are included from cement, chemical, waste to energy, refinery and power sectors.

Table 3-24 CO₂ captured and utilized in the Baltic-4 scenario

Cluster Location - City/Region	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions produced Mt/y	Number of emitters	CO ₂ emissions captured, Mt/y	CO ₂ emissions used, Mt/y
Bydgoszcz	Energy from waste	0.16	1	0.15	0.02
Piechcin, Janikowo, Inowroclaw	Cement, chemical, lime	1.88	4	1.79	0.18
Wloclawek	Power-natural gas, Amonia	1.81	2	1.72	0.17
Plock	Chemical, refinery, Power	4.33	4	4.11	0.41
Total for Baltic-4		8.19	11	7.77	0.77

3.4.4 Main advantages

Within the value chain area there are a number of onshore saline aquifer structures, two of them selected in this scenario as storage sites, of likely a quite high storage capacity and located close to the considered industrial emission sources. This makes it possible not only to easily develop but also to enlarge the value chain, adding more emitters located in north-central part of Poland. The relevant legal framework allowing development of CO₂ onshore storage and transport infrastructure in Poland is in progress and likely will be completed in 2025. Because installations of stakeholders of ongoing PCI ECO2CEE project (Orlen refinery and Holcim Lafarge cement plant where capture unit is being developed under Go4ECOPlanet project) belong to this value chain, onshore storage could be another option for these stakeholders, besides the scheduled railway and then ship transport through Gdańsk CO₂ terminal to store under the North Sea seabed.

3.4.5 Main challenges

The main challenges are regulatory and social. The legal framework to make it possible to develop CO₂ onshore storage and transport infrastructure is still in progress. Because storage sites land areas are owned by local landlords, their acceptance as well as of local communities is to be gained. Governmental financial support to CCS/CCUS projects in Poland is not yet envisaged.

3.5 Comparison of the Baltic Projects

After conducting the semiquantitative analysis of studied technical and nontechnical parameters, we prioritised a list of CCUS value chains based on their level of readiness. Notably, the cross-border Baltic-2 and Baltic-3 CCUS projects emerged as the readiest. The Baltic-2 project centres on both onshore and offshore storage, while the Baltic-3 project is focused exclusively on onshore storage.

The key internal strengths of these two value chains include a high storage capacity due to excellent reservoir properties, the considerable thickness of primary cap rocks, a high density of total emissions per unit distance, and other strong technical parameters. The main external opportunities stem from favourable CCS policies and regulations in Denmark, where CO₂ storage sites are located. Germany, Sweden, and Denmark are Contracting Parties to the LP.

However, Germany faces a significant risk as it has not submitted a declaration for provisional application to the IMO. Such a declaration and a bilateral agreement or arrangement are necessary before Germany can export CO₂ for offshore storage. In contrast, Sweden and Denmark have submitted their declarations and are now able to export CO₂ for offshore storage.

The Baltic-1 and Baltic-4 value chains are categorised as less ready due to regulatory risks associated with CO₂ storage onshore in Latvia and Poland, respectively. Industrial-scale CO₂ storage is not permitted in Latvia. In Poland, CO₂ storage is now permitted offshore in the Baltic Sea. However, due to the prohibition of CO₂ storage in the Baltic Sea by the Helsinki Convention, it is currently not allowed to inject CO₂ offshore in the Baltic. Regulations related to onshore storage are still under development. Despite the planned changes in the CCS regulations and other available technical strengths, these regulatory changes in Latvia and Poland may take additional time, and the risks should be seriously considered.

The Baltic-2 projects was selected for the further techno-economic modelling and business case in the WP4, based on its highest impact on climate change and the highest level of readiness in the Baltic Region.

3.6 Mediterranean-1: Turkiye - Greece offshore CCUS project

In the D3.1 it was assumed by authors of Med-2 project that ratio of CO₂ contributing to CCUS will depend on the type of industry, as other decarbonization levers can also be used to reduce CO₂ emissions. They assumed 35 % CCUS contribution from chemical plants, 25% for iron & steel, 50 % for refineries and power, 65 % for Cement and lime, 80% from waste to energy and 85% for hydrogen Table 3-25 (Shogenova et al, 2025). For this approach CO₂ use was calculated as 30% from CO₂ captured. This approach is used for all the Mediterranean projects.

Table 3-25 Summary of CO₂ emitter sector, and CCUS contribution used in the calculations (CO₂ captured) (Shogenova et al, 2024, p. 92-93, Sousa et al, 2024 p.29).

Type of industry	CCUS contribution, % (captured CO ₂)	Source	Comments
Chemicals	35	IEA (2020) report	Several other means such as electrification, process efficiency, fuel change exists. We will use values from IEA.
Iron & steel	25	IEA (2020) report	The industry is looking at several other decarbonisation pathways and changes in their processes
Refineries	50	Assumption	Other means such as electrification, process efficiency, fuel charge exists. However, refineries must also use their by-product as fuel so there are more non-reducible emissions. Hence, an average value is proposed.
Power	50	Assumption	Average value taken with the assumption that some of the power plant will convert to biogenic fuel
Cement/Lime	65	IEA (2020) report	Process emissions are still to be handled
Hydrogen	85	Assumption	Less other decarbonisation options for existing installations exists, unless changing the whole plant to Green H ₂ , therefor a high percentage is proposed.
Fibre & pulp	85	Assumption	Less other decarbonisation options and biogenic CO ₂
Waste to Energy	80	Assumption	Less other decarbonisation options and biogenic CO ₂

The Med 1 value chain includes two emission clusters, namely the Soma cluster and the İzmir Aliağa cluster in Turkiye, and an offshore storage site in Greece. The CO₂ emissions in Soma cluster are firstly transported to İzmir Aliağa via an onshore pipeline (120 km), then the total CO₂ emissions in both clusters are transported from İzmir Aliağa to Prinos storage site via a ship (360 km).

Figure 3.5 Med-1 value chain indicating the emission sources in Soma cluster (blue circles), emission sources in İzmir-Aliğa cluster (green circles), and the Prinos Basin as the offshore storage site (red oblique). The onshore pipeline transport route from Soma cluster to İzmir Aliğa cluster is shown by the red line, whereas the offshore ship transport route from İzmir Aliğa cluster to Prinos Basin is shown by the brown line.

Table 3-26 Parameters of the Med 1 value chain

Cluster ID	Involved countries	Total CO ₂ emissions, Mt/y	Emission sources	Emission clusters	Storage sites	Number of storage sites	Total capacity, Mt	Distance from emissions to storage, km	Emission clusters per country	Storage sites per cluster
Med-1	Turkiye, Greece	40	16	2	Prinos	1	1350	168 (onland) - 360 (ship)	1	0.5

3.6.1 CO₂ emissions and transport

The share of carbon emissions potentially addressed by CCUS is estimated according to the industrial sector using the methodology developed for the Mediterranean region and shown in Table 3-25 (Shogenova et al, 2024).

Table 3-27 Pipelines distance from CO₂ emitters to the storage sites for Mediterranean-1 scenario.

Country	Emitter ID	Facility name	City/Region	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions Mt/y	Captured emissions Mt/y	Storage site	Pipeline segments	Pipeline length (km)
Turkiye	E_TU_69	Soma Kolin Termik Santrali	Soma	Power	5.69	2.70	Prinos	Soma Kolin to Soma B	17.0
Turkiye	E_TU_64	Soma B Termik Santrali	Soma	Power	11.05	5.25	Prinos	Soma B to Soma A	0.64
Turkiye	E_TU_88	Soma A Termik Santrali	Soma	Power	0.42	0.20	Prinos	Soma A to Soma Çimento	11.25
Turkiye	E_TU_45	Soma Çimento	Soma	Cement	0.68	0.42	Prinos	Soma Çimento to Gathering Facility	120
Total for Soma Cluster					17.84	8.57			148.89
Turkiye	E_TU_183	İzmir Demir Çelik	Aliağa	Iron & Steel	0.11	0.03	Prinos	İzmir Demir Çelik to İzmir Enerji	0.57
Turkiye	E_TU_75	İzdemir Enerji	Aliağa	Power	5.32	2.53	Prinos	İzdemir Enerji to Gathering Facility	2.34
Turkiye	E_TU_135	Petkim Petrokimya	Aliağa	Power	0.72	0.34	Prinos	Petkim Petrokimya to Gathering Facility	2.65
Turkiye	E_TU_147	Tüpraş Termik Santrali	Aliağa	Power	0.30	0.14	Prinos	Tüpraş Termik Santrali to Petkim	1.78
Turkiye	E_TU_170	Petkim	Aliağa	Chemicals (Other)	1.98	0.66	Prinos	Petkim to Gathering Facility	3.18
Turkiye	E_TU_180	Ege Çelik Endüstrisi	Aliağa	Iron & Steel	0.16	0.04	Prinos	Ege Çelik Endüstrisi to Habaş Doğalgaz	1.36
Turkiye	E_TU_188	Özkan Demir Çelik	Aliağa	Iron & Steel	0.10	0.02	Prinos	Özkan Demir Çelik to Habaş Doğalgaz	0.51

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Turkiye	E_TU_116	Habaş Doğalgaz	Aliağa	Power	3.39	1.61	Prinos	Habaş Doğalgaz to Gathering Facility	2.42
Turkiye	E_TU_111	Enka Doğalgaz	Aliağa	Power	4.94	2.35	Prinos	Enka Doğalgaz to Gathering Facility	2.53
Turkiye	E_TU_174	Habaş	Aliağa	Iron & Steel	0.36	0.09	Prinos	Habaş to Gathering Facility	1.53
Turkiye	E_TU_169	Star Rafinerisi	Aliağa	Refineri es	2.44	1.16	Prinos	Star Rafinerisi to Petkim Petrokim ya	0.7
Turkiye	E_TU_167	İzmir Rafinerisi	Aliaga	Refineri es	2.35	1.12	Prinos	İzmir Rafinerisi to Tüpraş Termik Santralı	1.15
Total for Aliaga Cluster					22.17	10.07			20.72
Total for Med-1					40.00	18.64			

3.6.2 CO₂ storage site

Table 3-28 Properties of CO₂ storage sites in the Med 1 value chain (a)

Country	Storage site ID	Storage type	Storage unit	Daughter Unit	Lithology	Area, km ²	Net to gross ratio	Depth Top, m	Thickness, m	Porosity, %	Permeability, mD	Temperature, °C	Pressure, MpA	CO ₂ density, kg/m ³
Greece	S_GR6	DSA	Prinos sand	Prinos aquifer	Sandstone	800	0.8	2400	260	18	50	110	31	724.77

Table 3-29 Properties of CO₂ storage sites in the Med 1 value chain (b)

Daughter Unit	Seal lithology	Seal Thickness, m	Secondary seals	Boundary condition	Seff	Capacity mean	SR	Seismic survey	Wells	Abandoned wells	Modeling	Baseline data
Prinos Mioocene DSA	Evaporites	150				1350	1					

3.6.3 CO₂ use options in Med-1

In Turkey, power sector remains the main contributor to CO₂ emissions Table 3-27 and needs to be addressed as a priority for decarbonisation.

Besides, CO₂ use options are studied by stakeholders through two main EU-funded projects. COZMOS is one of the main EU-funded project including Turkish industrial partners like

Tüpras and Linde Gas, that aims to provide breakthrough technology for the conversion of CO₂ to C₃ fuels and chemical building blocks. This project gathers 11 partners from the steel, refining, chemical and engineering sectors, research and technology organisations and universities, working on the development of innovative catalyst process technologies that will fit the expectations to obtain value-added products.

COZMOS technology will decrease CO₂ emissions by 1.9 tons CO₂ for every ton of C₃ product produced, with expected reductions in CO₂ emissions of 0.4 Mtons CO₂/yr in 2030 and 2.2 Mtons CO₂/year from 2034. It will design a flexible solution adaptable to local requirements and different industries. COZMOS technology will contribute to a circular economy and the replacement of fossil fuels, leading to a decrease in CO₂ emissions and European dependence on fossil resources. Tüpraş has an important share of 776,375 € in this project, which received 4M€ subvention. Tüpras remains a small emitter regarding emissions of Soma and Aliaga clusters though (COZMOS, 2024).

Petrochemical company Petkim that has higher CO₂ emissions in those clusters, covering 12% of petrochemical product demand in Turkey, is currently involved in CO2Fokus EU-funded project aiming to produce DiMethylEther by direct use of CO₂ hydrogenation in a single-step process, instead of going through methanol synthesis. Different market opportunities of DME are studied: as a fuel, LPG blend (Liquified Petroleum Gas), hydrogen carrier, aerosol, chemical solvent and power generation (CO2Fokus, 2024).

The interest in renewable DME and in LPG blending, as well as the considerable LPG market are key drivers for the DME market in Turkey. Turkey has the largest LPG market in the world: in 2019, the Turkish LPG market meets an estimated 13% of the country's total demand for automotive fuels and accounts for 76% of Turkey's total LPG consumption (WLPGA, 2019). Additionally, LPG is a popular automotive fuel in the country (Autogas) and widely available at fuelling stations.

From the produced 40 Mt of CO₂ emission, 18.64 Mt/y of CO₂ will be captured from which 5.59 Mt could be utilised in Med-1 scenario Table 3-30.

Table 3-30 CO₂ captured and utilised in the Med-1 Scenario

CLUSTER NAME	TOTAL CO ₂ EMISSIONS Mt/y	NUMBER OF EMITTERS	CO ₂ EMISSION CAPTURED, Mt/y	CO ₂ FOR UTILIZATION (30% of CO ₂ captured), Mt/y
Soma Cluster	17.84	4	8.57	2.57
Aliaga Cluster	22.17	12	10.07	3.02
Total Med-1	40.0	16	18.64	5.59

3.6.4 Main Advantages

Mediterranean-1 (Med-1) value chain could enhance energy and environmental cooperation between Türkiye and Greece, fostering collaboration on regional initiatives. Capturing CO₂ emissions from industrial regions like Aliaga and Soma can significantly reduce their negative impact on climate and the environment. This value chain could be a critical step towards Türkiye meeting its commitments under the Paris Agreement and aligning with the European Green Deal. Besides, the capacity of the selected storage site, Prinos Basin, is high enough for the optimal CO₂ storage duration, and storing CO₂ in this field can contribute to the local economy and the energy sector in the region.

3.6.5 Main Challenges

The Mediterranean-1 (Med-1) value chain includes technical, economical, and mainly the social and regulatory challenges. To start with, the inaccessibility of annual, sector-based CO₂ emission data restricted the mapping of CO₂ emission sources in Türkiye. Accordingly, instead of real emission data, the IPCC's reference approaches (IPCC, 2006) were used in the calculation of CO₂ emissions only from the selected industries, which might have led to uncertainties in total CO₂ emissions. Besides, the Med-1 value chain includes two countries, both of which are in seismically active regions, which would create technical challenges particularly during the CO₂ storage stage. From the economical point of view, the Med-1 value chain requires adaptation of new infrastructure such as pipelines or ships, which would result in significant investments to ensure the economic viability of the project. In the absence of carbon pricing mechanisms or carbon credits, covering these costs might be even more challenging. Last but foremost, the main challenge for Mediterranean-1 value chain can be mentioned as the international regulations. Neither Türkiye nor Greece is involved in London Protocol, which would lay an obstacle for the transportation and storage of CO₂ in offshore formations.

3.7 Mediterranean 2 (Med-2): France – Spain CCUS offshore project

The Mediterranean-2 CCUS scenario is a transboundary project from France to Spain planned for 20 years. It includes three clusters with 32 CO₂ emitters from two countries and one storage site offshore Spain in DSA. The included industrial clusters are the Tarragona (5 emitters) and the Barcelona (9 emitters) clusters in Spain, and the Fos-Marseille cluster in France, annually producing 23.82 Mt CO₂. The geological storage site Castellón is located offshore Tarragona in the Ebro Basin. The captured 9.77 Mt CO₂ will be collected in the three clusters hubs, partly used depending on the viability of the CO₂ use options and the remaining CO₂ will be transported and stored in Castellón site. In the reference case, an onshore gathering hub at Tarragona port will collect the CO₂ from the three clusters: CO₂ from local Tarragona emitters, CO₂ from Barcelona cluster sent by an offshore dense phase pipeline and CO₂ from Fos-Marseille cluster (18 emitters) transported by ships. From the onshore gathering hub at Tarragona, a single dense phase offshore pipeline will send the collected CO₂ to the subsea system including subsea injection wells around 60 km away (Shogenova et al, 2024).

CO₂ flow rates to be captured, transported and stored are limited in Mediterranean-2 project by the recently reported storage capacity of the Castellon site offshore Spain (200 Mt). Various possibilities for CO₂ utilization are also being considered on the basis of CCU feasibility studies and projects in France and Spain. The CCUS scenario is mapped on Figure 3.6 and synthesized in Table 3-31.

Table 3-31 Main technical parameters of Mediterranean-2 value chain.

Cluster ID	Involved countries	Total CO ₂ emissions captured, Mt/y	Emission sources	Emission clusters	Storage sites	Number of storage sites	Total capacity, Mt	Distance from emissions to storage, km	Emission clusters per country	Storage sites per cluster
<u>Mediterranean 2</u>	Spain, France	9.77	32	3	Castellón	1	200	48-470	2 in Spain, 1 in France	0.33

3.7.1 CO₂ emitters

In the Med-2 the approach to calculate CO₂ captured emissions is shown in the Table 3-25. Three industrial clusters are considered for the Med-2 value chain. In Spain, the Tarragona cluster comprises 5 emitters with total captured emissions of 1.98 Mt/y. The Barcelona cluster gathers 9 emitters for a total amount of captured CO₂ of 2.25 Mt/y. In France, the Fos-Marseille cluster is the biggest, with 18 emitters and 5.54 Mt/y of captured emissions. In the whole value chain, a total amount of 9.77 Mt would be captured annually (Table 3-32).

Figure 3.6 Map of the Mediterranean-2 CCUS value chain.

Table 3-32 CO₂ emitters and emissions volumes included in three clusters of the Mediterranean-2 Value Chain

Emitter ID	Facility name	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions 2022, Mt/y	CO ₂ captured, Mt/y	Fossil CO ₂ captured, Mt/y	Biogenic CO ₂ captured, Mt/y
S_ES_4	Repsol Refineria Tarragona	Refineries	1.968	0.935	0.933	0.00095
S_ES_24	Repsol Quimica	Chemicals	0.851	0.283	0.277	0.0058

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S_ES_28	Dow Chemical Iberica (Dow Nord)	Chemicals	0.985	0.327	0.327	0.0
S_ES_47	Tarragona Power	Power	0.403	0.191	0.191	0.0
S_ES_77	Hyco (La Pobla De Mafument)	Hydrogen	0.303	0.244	0.244	0.0
TOTAL for Tarragona cluster			4.510	1.981	1.974	0.007
E_ES_13	Central Termica De Cicle Combinat (Sant Adria De Besos - Grup 4)	Power	0.648	0.308	0.308	0.0
E_ES_70	Central Termica De Cicle Combinat (Sant Adria De Besos - Grup 3)	Power	0.585	0.278	0.278	0.0
E_ES_20	Cementos Molins Industrial (Sant Vicenc Dels Horts)	Cement/Lime	0.934	0.577	0.507	0.07
E_ES_55	Fabrica De Montcada (Lafargeholcim Espana Sau)	Cement/Lime	0.426	0.263	0.211	0.052
E_ES_80	Central Termica De Cicle Combinat (Sant Adria De Besos - Grup 5)	Power	0.787	0.374	0.374	0.0
E_ES_103	Planta De Valoritzacio Energetica De Sant Adria De Besos	Energy from waste	0.285	0.217	0.109	0.108
E_ES_130	Barcelona Cartonboard	Paper and pulp	0.137	0.110	0.110	0.0
E_ES_144	Compania Espanola De Laminacion (Celsa 1-4)	Iron & Steel	0.148	0.0352	0.0352	0.0
E_ES_232	Central Termica De Cicle Combinat (Port De Barcelona)	Power	0.356	0.089	0.089	0.0
TOTAL for Barcelona cluster			4.306	2.251	2.022	0.229

D.3.3 A generic framework for selection of the most promising CCUS value chains

E_FR_2	Arcelormittal Mediterranee	Iron & Steel	6.447	1.531	1.531	0
E_FR_8	Naphtachimie	Chemicals (other)	1.431	0.476	0.476	0
E_FR_10	Petroineos Manufacturing France Sas	Refineries	1.117	0.531	0.531	0
E_FR_15	Basell Polyolefines France Sas (Berre)	Chemicals	0.444	0.148	0.148	0
E_FR_17	Centre Production Thermique Ponreau - CCG de Martigues	Power	1.446	0.687	0,687	0
E_FR_28	Esso Raffinage Sas	Refineries	0.677	0.322	0,322	0
E_FR_55	Engie Thermique France - Cycofos	Power	0.732	0.348	0,348	0
E_FR_62	Lafargeholcim Ciments	Cement	0.368	0.227	0.210	0.017
E_FR_63	Evere Sas	Energy from waste	0.42	0.319	0.129	0.190
E_FR_65	Centrale Thermique de COMBIGOLFE	Power	0.574	0.273	0,273	0
E_FR_95	Total Raffinage France	Refineries	0.199	0.095	0,095	0
E_FR_122	Cifc	Cement/Lime	0.189	0.117	0.117	0
E_FR_132	Air Liquide France Industrie (Alfi)	Hydrogen	0.134	0.089	0.089	0
E_FR_136	Lyondell Chimie France Sas (Fos)	Chemicals (other)	0.205	0.068	0.068	0
E_FR_143	Chaux De Provence Sacam	Cement/Lime	0.107	0.066	0.066	0
E_FR_145	Imerys Aluminates Sa	Cement/Lime	0.157	0.097	0.097	0
E_FR_146	Kem One France	Chemicals (other)	0.155	0.052	0.052	0

E_FR_151	Lyondell Basell Services France Sas	Power	0.193	0.092	0.092	0
TOTAL for Fos-Marseille cluster			14.995	5.535	5.328	0.207
TOTAL			23.82	9.77	9.33	0.44

3.7.2 Storage site

The storage site considered for Mediterranean-2 CCUS value chain is an offshore storage site near Tarragona in the Ebro basin (Spain) with a capacity over 200 Mt. The targeted reservoir is in the upper Miocene Castellón Sandstones, which runs from approximately 1600 m to 1900m, overlain by the Ebro clays (Pliocene). The storage site is detailed in Shogenova (2024). The reservoir's parameters are summarized in [Table 3-33](#). Seal thickness is extrapolated from well data (Salmonete-1 and Castellon B-13 (IGME, 2024)).

[Table 3-33 Reservoir parameters for Castellon storage site.](#)

Storage site parameters	Units	
Country		Spain
Site name		Castellón
Onshore / offshore		Offshore
Reservoir Lithology		Upper Miocene Castellón Sandstone
Top depth	m	1600
Thickness	m	300-600
Reservoir pressure @1600m	MPa	16
Reservoir temperature @1600m	°C	74
Porosity	%	14-20
Permeability	D	0.010-0.500
Average Storage Capacity	Mt	>200
Cap rocks		Ebro Clays
Seal thickness	m	900

3.7.3 CO₂ use options in Med-2

In the Mediterranean-2 scenario, CCU facilities are located in the vicinity of the gathering station within each cluster, which is a good advantage for CCU deployment. Scenarios of CCU capacity deployment are presented in [Table 3-34](#).

Table 3-34 Scenarios of CCU capacity deployment in the Mediterranean-2 value chain

Country	Gathering station	Captured CO ₂ from emitters, Mt/y	Captured CO ₂ from emitters for CCU, Mt/y	Number of CCU installations per cluster	Average capture capacity of CCU installation, kt/y	Average Methanol capacity of CCU installation, kt/y	Average Synthetic Jet Fuel capacity of CCU installation, kt/y
Spain	Tarragona	1.98	0.59	3	200 Assuming CO ₂ capacity comparable to the Green MEIGA project	144	56
Spain	Barcelona	2.25	0.68	4	170 Assuming CO ₂ capacity comparable to the Green MEIGA project	123	47
France	Marseille	5.54	1.66	7	238 Assuming CO ₂ capacity comparable to the eM-Rhône	171	67
	Total	9.77	2.93	12		1779	890

Among funded by EC projects there are also Repsol projects such as the Ecoplanta in Morell (Tarragona) for the use of non-recyclable municipal waste to generate methanol – and ‘T-Hynet’ also in Tarragona for the production of green hydrogen in the Tarragona refinery for local consumption. Among the projects awarded in the 2023 call are the ‘TarraCO₂-Storage’ projects by Repsol in Tarragona (REVE, 2024).

E-methanol and e-SAF were defined as the most promising products to be developed in this value chain for the needs of the different clusters.

Table 3-35 Overview of possible CO₂ for capture and utilisation for Med-2

Cluster name	Total CO ₂ emissions, Mt/y	Number of emitters	CO ₂ emission captured (based on sector ref. table 3-11), Mt/y	CO ₂ for utilization (30% of capture, Mt/year)
Tarragona	4.51	5	1.97	0.59
Barcelona	4.31	10	2.25	0.68
France	14.995	18	5.55	1.67
Total Med-2	23.82	33	9.77	2.93

Using the same methodology and assumptions than in part 3.1.3, 9,87 Mt/y of CO₂ should be addressed by CCUS in Med-2. It is also assumed that 30% of captured CO₂ will go to utilisation, meaning that 0,99 MT/y should be used in the Med-2. A full overview by cluster is shown in Table 3-35, with total CO₂ emission, captured emission and CO₂ for utilisation.

3.7.4 CO₂ Transport

An onshore gathering hub at Tarragona would collect the CO₂ from the three clusters: CO₂ from local Tarragona emitters, CO₂ from Barcelona sent by an offshore dense phase pipeline and CO₂ from Fos-Marseille transported by ships. From the onshore gathering hub at Tarragona, a single dense phase offshore pipeline will send the collected CO₂ to the subsea system including subsea injection wells around 58 km away. Inside each cluster, a local pipeline network is designed to transport CO₂ in gas phase from the various sources to a gathering facility. Transport modes for Med-2 value chain are detailed in Table 3-36.

Table 3-36 Transport options for the clusters in the Mediterranean-2

From	To	Transport mode	Phase	Length, km	Volume, Mt/y
Tarragona emitters	Tarragona gathering facility	Pipeline	Gas	15.684	1.981
Barcelona emitters	Barcelona gathering facility	Pipeline (2 parts)	Gas	8.550 and 40.526	0.263 and 1.987
Fos-Marseille emitters	Fos gathering facility	<i>Out of scope</i>			
Fos-Marseille gathering facility	Tarragona export hub	Shipping	Liquid	470	5.535
Barcelona gathering facility	Tarragona export hub	Offshore pipeline	Dense	106	2.25
Tarragona export hub	Offshore injection site	Offshore pipeline	Dense	48.1	9.77

3.7.5 Main Advantages

The Med-2 CCUS value chain would enable significant reduction of the emissions in the selected clusters. Fos-Marseille cluster included in the CO₂ value chain is more advanced in terms of development as the region was selected by E.U. as a Project of Common Interest (PCI) for CO₂ export terminal. REPSOL EXPLORACIÓN has applied for an exploration permit for CO₂ storage for the Castellón site ("TARRACO2"), paving the way for developing a CO₂ storage offshore Spain.

3.7.6 Main Challenges

The announced storage capacity of 200 Mt would allow storing the value chain's emissions during no more than 20 years. This could be challenging for the economic viability of the value chain.

3.8 Mediterranean 3 (Med-3): Southern France onshore CCUS project

Map of Beaucaire CCUS value chain

Figure 3.7 Scenario for capture, transport and storage for the Beaucaire value chain.

The Mediterranean 3 value chain is a local-scale scenario in Southern France involving two emitters close to Beaucaire and a storage site located about 30 km away. The 2 industrial sites are a paper plant and a cement plant, emitting 1.17 Mt/y in total. The storage option is onshore saline aquifer site Haut d'Albaron, of storage capacity 34 Mt. The emission sources and the storage site can be connected by an onshore pipeline. Figure 3.7 locates emitters, storage and transport and presents the main features of the Beaucaire value chain.

Table 3-37 Parameters of the Mediterranean 3 value chain.

Cluster ID	Involvement countries	Total CO2 emissions, Mt/y	Emission sources	Emission clusters	Storage sites	Number of storage sites	Total capacity, Mt	Distance from emissions to storage, km	Emission clusters per country	Storage sites per cluster
<u>Mediterranean 3</u>	France	1.17	2	1	Onshore Haut d'Albaron	1	34	32.6-38.5	1	1

3.8.1 CO₂ Emitters

Located 45 km northwest from Fos-sur-Mer, the Beaucaire cluster regroups only two emitters: a Ciments Calcia cement plant and a Fibre Excellence Tarascon paper plant, totalling CO₂

The share of CO₂ emissions potentially captured is estimated according to the industrial sector using the methodology presented in Shogenova et al, 2025 for Mediterranean region and repeated in the [Table 3-25](#).

Table 3-38 Beaucaire cluster - Emitters sites feature.

Emitter ID	Facility name	Sector	CO ₂ emission, Mt/y	CO ₂ emissions from biomass, Mt/y	CO ₂ captured, Mt/y	Bio-CO ₂ captured, Mt/y
E_FR_36	Fibre Excellence Tarascon	Paper and pulp	0.590	0.541	0.476	0.437
E_FR_38	Ciments Calcia	Cement	0.578	0.031	0.357	0.019
Total Beaucaire cluster			1.168	0.572	0.833	0.456

3.8.2 CO₂ Storage

The storage site is Haut d'Albaron structure, one of the targets in Upper Jurassic carbonate-reservoirs in "structural horst" identified in the VASCO project (Grataloup et al., 2012). The reservoir features were gathered by Carneiro and Mesquita (2020) and are listed in Table 3-39. The site is defined by Grataloup et al. (2012) as good reservoir properties. Exploration wells in the area identified high permeability dolomites with artesian water flow of 800 l/min. An estimation of the reservoir permeability was made in the GeoCapacity project with a 300 mD value.

Table 3-39 Technical features of the storage site for Beaucaire scenario.

Storage Site ID	S_FR1
Storage type	Deep Saline Aquifer
Formation	Upper Jurassic
Storage unit	Haut d'Albaron
Lithology	Fractured limestone
Area net-to- gross ratio	80
Depth top, m	200
Thickness, m	865
Porosity type	Secondary
Porosity expected	0.15
Permeability, mD	300
Temperature, °C	45.5

CO ₂ density, kg/m ³	260
Seal	Plaisancian
Seal lithology	Shales
Seal thickness, m	66-164
Capacity mean, Mt	34
SRL	2

3.8.3 CO₂ use options in Med-3

In the Beaucaire area, 46% of CO₂ emissions are coming from paper industry and are considered as biogenic, which is an opportunity for CO₂ utilisation. Nevertheless, industrial emitters in this cluster do not communicate so far on their strategy for CO₂ utilisation.

Additionally, 100 km at the North of Med-3 cluster, CO₂ use for catalytic methanol production is considered with a potential of 200 kt CO₂/y through eM-Rhône project on the chemical platform of Les-Roches-Roussillon. Presence of CCU facility in this area may encourage the utilisation of CO₂ in Med-3 cluster. Emitted CO₂ could also be transported to the Fos-Marseille hub through pipeline along the Rhône axis, where another CCU facilities are projected to be installed for e-methanol production and fuels.

Using the same methodology and assumptions than in [Table 3-25](#), 0.83 Mt/y of CO₂ should be captured in Med-3. It is also assumed that 30% of captured CO₂ will go to utilisation, meaning that 0.25 Mt/y should be used in the Med-3. A full overview by cluster is shown in [Table 3-40](#), with total emission, captured emission and utilisation.

[Table 3-40 Overview of possible CO₂ for capture and utilisation for Med-3](#)

Cluster name	Total CO ₂ emissions, Mt/y	Number of emitters	CO ₂ emission captured, Mt/y	CO ₂ for utilization (30% of capture), Mt/y
Beaucaire	1.168	2	0.833	0.25
Total Med-3	1.168	2	0.833	0.25

3.8.4 CO₂ Transport

The emission sources and the storage site can be connected by an onshore pipeline of total length 32.6 (option 1) or 38.5 km (option 2), whether using more or less direct route or, to some extent, existing gas pipeline corridors ([Figure 3.7](#)).

3.8.5 Main Advantages

The storage capacity is adapted to the emissions volumes of the 2 neighbour plants. Such a project would offer a local solution to reduce emissions of the 2 Beaucaire plants for almost 30 years. Investments for transport infrastructures would be limited, as maximum distance would be less than 40 km.

3.8.6 Main Challenges

The Haut d'Albaron aquifer is a shallow reservoir (top at 200 m depth), implying that CO₂ would not be stored in a dense phase but in the gas phase, thus reducing the storage capacity. Despite the seal's thickness, low depth would raise more leakage concerns. Moreover, development of CO₂ storage and transport in this area could be challenging due to protected areas around (Natura2000, Bird protection area).

3.9 Mediterranean 4 (Med-4): Southern Italy – Greece CCUS onshore project with onshore and offshore transport

The Mediterranean 4 case includes onshore pipelines in the southern part of Italy, from Priolo Gargallo in southwest, and from Brindisi in east. The onshore storage site Brandanica, is situated close to Taranto (Figure 3.8). In addition to the pipeline system, we suggest ship transport from potentially France and Greece, with a harbour at Brindisi gives the key input parameters for the Med-4 including transport and storage in southern Italy and ship transport from emission hubs around Athen in Greece. A detail overview of the included emission sources for southern Italy and Athen region is shown in Table 3-42 and details about the storage site is summed in Table 3-43.

Figure 3.8 Overview map of Mediterranean 4, with CO₂ storage onland in southern Italy at Brandanica Storage Site. A pipeline is suggested, following the existing national gas pipeline path with transport from several CO₂ Emission Hubs. From southwest we have Priolo Gargallo, Messina, Cantanzaro emission hubs, and from east we have Brindisi and Taranto. In addition, we suggest including ship transport to harbour at Brindisi from Greece, and potentially France. Map from D3.2.

Table 3-41 Overview of Med-4 covering the southern Italy and emitters situated close to Athens (Greece).

Cluster ID	Involved countries	Total CO ₂ emissions, Mt/y	Emission sources	Emission clusters	Storage sites	Number of storage sites	Total capacity, Mt	Distance from emissions to storage, km	Emission clusters per country	Storage sites per cluster
Med-4	Italy, Greece	41.1	32	6	1	1	344-1376	Approx 500	Italy 5 and Greece 1	0.16

3.9.1 CO₂ Emitters

Table 3-42 Table for emission sources from southern Italy and close to Athens in Greece

EMITTER ID	FACILITY NAME	COMPANY NAME	STATE	INDUSTRY SECTOR	EMISSION TREND	CO ₂ EMISSIONS (t/y)
E_IT_5	Enel Produziane S.P.A.	Enel Produziane S.P.A.	Brindisi	Power	Falling	3 856 000
E_IT_6	Enipower S.P.A.	Enipower S.P.A.	Brindisi	Power	Growing	2.623 000
E_IT_92	Versalis S.P.A.	Versalis S.P.A.	Brindisi	Chemicals	Falling	370 000
E_IT_227	Firenze Fpso	Firenze Fpso	Brindisi	Oil & gas processing	Falling	42 000
Total Brindisi cluster						6 891 000
E_IT_2	ArcelorMittal Italia	ArcelorMittal Italia	Taranto	Iron & Steel	falling	5 246 000
E_IT_3	Arcelormittal Italy Energy S.R.L.	Taranto Energia S.R.L. In Amministrazione Straordinaria	Taranto	Power	growing	4 405 000
E_IT_25	Eni S.P.A.	Eni S.P.A.	Taranto	Refineries	growing	1 113 764
E_IT_52	Raffineria Di Taranto	Eni S.P.A.	Taranto	Refineries	falling	680000
E_IT_75	Italcementi Di Matera	Italcementi Spa	Matera	Cement	growing	478000
E_IT_103	Eni S.P.A.	Eni S.P.A.	Taranto	Refineries	growing	306000
E_IT_135	Tecnoparco Valbasento S.P.A.	Tecnoparco Valbasento S.P.A.	Matera	Power	growing	182 000
Total Taranto cluster						12 410 764

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E_IT_22	Edison S.P.A.	Edison S.P.A.	Catanzaro	Power	falling	1 346 000
Total Catanzaro cluster						1 346 000
E_IT_10	Raffineria Di Milazzo S.C.P.A.	Raffineria Di Milazzo S.C.P.A.	Messina	Refineries	falling	1 905 000
E_IT_21	A2A Energiefuture S.P.A.	A2A Energiefuture S.P.A.	Messina	Power	growing	1 347 000
E_IT_66	Termica Milazzo S.R.L.	Termica Milazzo S.R.L.	Messina	Power	growing	566 000
Total Messina cluster						3 818 000
E_IT_8	Esso Italiana S.R.L.	Esso Italiana S.R.L.	Siracusa	Refineries	growing	2 008 000
E_IT_15	Isab S.R.L.	Isab S.R.L.	Siracusa	Refineries	falling	1 677 000
E_IT_33	Erg Power S.R.L.	Erg Power S.R.L.	Siracusa	Power	falling	921 000
E_IT_44	Versalis S.P.A.	Versalis S.P.A.	Siracusa	Chemicals (other)	growing	805 000
E_IT_72	Cementeria Di Augusta	Buzzi Unicem Spa	Siracusa	Cement	growing	510 000
E_IT_73	Enel Produzione S.P.A.	Enel Produzione S.P.A.	Siracusa	Power	growing	510 000
E_IT_80	Sasol Italy S.P.A.	Sasol Italy S.P.A.	Siracusa	Chemicals (other)	growing	450 000
E_IT_116	Isab S.R.L.	Isab S.R.L.	Siracusa	Power	falling	208 000
E_IT_173	Air Liquide Italia Produzione S.R.L.	Air Liquide Italia Produzione S.R.L.	Siracusa	Hydrogen	falling	125 000
Total Priolo Gargallo cluster						7 214 000
E_GR_4	Hellenic Petroleum S.A	Hellenic Petroleum S.A	Attiki	Refineries	growing	1 920 000
E_GR_5	Titan Cement S.A. -Kamari Plant	Titan Sement S.A.	Attiki	Cement	falling	1 480 000

E_GR_6	Hellenic Petroleum S.A	Hellenic Petroleum S.A	Attiki	Refineries	growing	1 459 000
E_GR_29	Sanitary Landfill	Edsna	Attiki	Other	falling	225 000
E_GR_31	Halyps Building Materials S.A.	Heidelberg Cement Group	Attiki	Cement	falling	191 000
E_GR_3	Motor Oil (Hellas)	Motor Oil	Peloponnies	Refineries	growing	2141000
E_GR_24	Korinthos Power S.A	Korinthos Power S.A	Peloponnies	Power	falling	612000
E_GR_7	Ppc S.A. Ses Kerateas-Layrioy	Ppc S.A. Ses Kerateas-Layrioy	Attiki	Power	growing	1394000
Total Athen cluster						9 422 000

3.9.2 Storage site

Table 3-43 Properties of the Brandanica CO₂ storage site in the Med-4 value chain

Dau ghter Unit	Seal	Seal lithology	Seal thickness, m	Secondary seals	Boundary condition	Seff, %	Capacity mean, Mt	S R L	Seismic survey	Wells	Abandoned wells	Modeling	Base_line data
Late Pliocene	Cala bria, Late Pliocene	Clay and silty clay	71	-	Closed	1- 4	344-1376	2	2D	1	1	-	-

3.9.3 CO₂ use options in Med-4

Eni and Snam companies are mainly involved in Ravenna Carbon Capture and Storage CCS to reduce emissions from “hard-to-abate” industrial facilities. Ravenna hub is projected to become the world’s largest CO₂ storage site starting from 2027 with 4 Mt/y capacity by 2030 and 16 Mt/y capacity beyond. Besides, Eni also invests in research and innovation around CCU, for example, in mineralisation technology for the production of Supplementary Cementitious materials for the formulation of cements (ENI, 2024).

EU-funded RECODE project was dealing with the capture and utilisation of CO₂ coming from TITAN cement factory, the largest cement factory in Greece, CO₂ purification and production of additives that can be used as cement additives, like nano-CaCO₃, formic acid, oxalic acid and glycine. This project also included the integration of renewable electricity from low grad heat-based electricity power. The first two years of the project were dedicated to the development of key functional materials and process units at TRL 4-5, the third year on the assembly of single-process lines certified at TRL 5-6, and the testing at a cement manufacturing site (TITAN) of the TRL 6 integrated CO₂ process. Final workshop in September 2022 aimed to present the perspective of a circular economy approach within

cement industry that represents 18% of CO₂ emissions of Athens cluster inside Med-4 value chain (RECODE, 2024).

Eni company is also part of the Horizon Europe HERCCULES R&I project aiming to develop innovative CO₂ capture technologies for the cement and waste-to-energy sectors. Goal is to set-up demonstration plant in two cement plants and one waste-to-energy plant located in Northern Italy and in Greece (HERCCULES, 2024).

Using the same methodology and assumptions than in Table 3-25, 18,47 Mt/y of CO₂ should be captured in Med-4. It is also assumed that 30% of captured CO₂ will go to utilization, meaning that 5.54 Mt/y should be used in the Med-4. A full overview by cluster is shown in Table 3-44, with total CO₂ emission, captured CO₂ emission and CO₂ for utilisation.

Table 3-44 Overview of possible CO₂ for capture and utilisation for Med-4

CLUSTER NAME	TOTAL CO ₂ EMISSIONS, Mt/y	NUMBER OF EMITTERS	CO ₂ EMISSION FOR CAPTURE, Mt/y	CO ₂ FOR UTILIZATION (30% of capture, Mt/y)
Brindisi cluster	6.89	4	3.22	0.97
Taranto cluster	12.41	7	4.72	1.42
Catanzaro cluster	1.346	1	0.64	0.19
Messina cluster	3.818	3	1.81	0.54
Priolo cluster	7.214	9	3.36	1.01
Athens cluster	9.422	8	4.71	1.41
Total Med-4	41.1	32	18.47	5.54

3.9.4 CO₂ transport

Table 3-45 Transport distances (pipelines and ships)

Value chain	Emission cluster(s)	Number of emitters	Annual CO ₂ emissions (t/y)	Storage site(s)	Capacity (Mt)	Distance along pipeline gate to onland storage site (km)	Comment
Southern Italy	Brindisi	4	6 891 000	Onshore Bradanica S_IT8	344-1376	110	-
	Taranto	7	12 410 764			50	5 km to exiting pipe gate
	Catanzaro	1	1 346 000			181	38.2 km distance to existing pipeline gate
	Messina	3	3 818 000			312	-
	Priolo Garallo	9	7 205 000			403	73,1 km distance to existing pipeline gate

Value chain	Emission cluster(s)	Number of emitters	Annual CO ₂ emissions (t/y)	Storage site(s)	Capacity (Mt)	Distance along pipeline gate to onland storage site (km)	Comment
	TOTAL (Italy)	24	31 670 764			Total pipeline 513 km	In addition: 116 km pipeline to connect to main pipeline gate
Greece	Attiki (close to Athen)	8	9 422 000			Total Ship transport (approx.900 km)	From Athen to Brindisi with ship

3.9.5 Main advantages

The main advantages for Med-4 are the CO₂ storage site with high capacity and good caprocks, with many potential emitters hubs within a short distance, using pipelines from nearby industry clusters.

Cross-border clusters from Greece and France can be included. Very good CO₂ use options could be assumed from the industrial sectors represented including cement plants, iron and steel, refineries and chemical plants.

3.9.6 Main challenges

Main challenges are represented by seismic risks in Italy and by the fact that the first permit for CO₂ storage in Italy is given only for experimental storage in depleted oil and gas fields offshore (given now for the first stage injection in Ravenna depleted gas field) (INECP-Italy, 2024). Densely populated area and Natura 2000 within the storage site are additional challenges for onshore storage site.

3.10 Comparison of the Mediterranean Projects

In the Mediterranean Region, Mediterranean-2, -3 and -4 value chains, which include correspondingly emission sources and storage sites in Spain (M-2), France (M-3), Italy and Greece (M-4), are assessed as more ready, while M-1, including CO₂ emissions from Türkiye and CO₂ storage in Greece as less ready, considering the regulatory risks. There is a lack of CCS regulations and CO₂ capture and transport infrastructures in Türkiye. Türkiye and Greece are not Contracting Parties to the LP and are therefore not bound by its requirements for cross-border CO₂ transport (i.e. declaration of provisional application and arrangement/agreement). The study closes with an overview of readiness and recommendations for advancing ready and less ready cases toward CCUS implementation. Some projects in both regions also have risks for the storage site area (external group 1).

Italy is planning to implement an Amendment and provisional application to Article 6. However, the technical parameters of the storage site in France M-3 (Haut d'Albaron) are not qualified for the needed requirements (internal technical weakness). Technical risks for the area around the storage site (external group 1) in Italy and Greece: seismic risks should be checked for the storage site areas. Most countries have risks connected with the location of Natura 2000 areas close to the storage sites or intersected with storage sites.

The Mediterranean-2 project was selected for the further techno-economic modelling and business case in the CCUS ZEN project, based on its relatively high level of readiness and impact on climate change in the Mediterranean Region. M-4 project has lower readiness and

M-1 project has the lowest readiness, and they both have seismic risks, despite higher impact on climate change compared to M-2 project (Table 2-1).

4 SWOT Analysis of Value Chains

4.1 Internal and External Groups of Factors

Internal technical groups include 1) CO₂ emission plants, 2) CO₂ storage sites, 3) available and planned infrastructure, and 4) CO₂ use options.

An external technical group including 1) characteristics of the area around the storage site and non-technical external groups 1) social, 2) political development, 3) International and national regulations, 4) MRV (Monitoring Reporting and Verification), 5) Financial parameters, 6) Readiness of CCUS value chain - were analysed for opportunities and risks.

Table 4-1. Internal and external groups of factors in SWOT analysis

INTERNAL GROUP Strength and Weakness	EXTERNAL GROUP	
	Opportunities and Threats (Risks)	
Technical	Technical	Non-technical
CO ₂ emission plants		Social
		Political development
CO ₂ storage sites	Area around the storage site	Regulatory
Infrastructure (available and planned)		MRV (Monitoring Reporting and Verification)
CO ₂ use options		Financial

4.2 Internal Factors Assessment for two regions

Among the main strengths of the technical group (1) we considered the piloting/planning of CO₂ capture, CO₂ use options, and hydrogen production. Porosity and permeability of the reservoir rocks, quality of the cap rock, CO₂ storage capacity and Storage Readiness Level (SRL) (Akhurst, et al, 2021), were analysed in the group (2) CO₂ storage sites. Availability of the natural gas pipelines, total CO₂ emissions per distance unit, wells in operation, availability of the offshore infrastructure and planned PCI project were parameters analysed in the group (3) infrastructure. The parameters analysed in the technical group (4): CO₂ use projects in operation, development or R&D phase, amount of CO₂ which could be used in the cluster and possible revenues.

We created the hierarchy of the analysis on internal assessment (Table 4-2), which already includes quantitative parameters.

Table 4-2 . Hierarchy of analysis on internal assessment.in SWOT analysis

SWOT group	SWOT Aspects	SWOT factors	Polarity
Internal assessment	CO ₂ emission plants	(I1) Number of countries	+
		(I2) Number of clusters	+
		(I3) Number of plants	+
		(I4) Fossil CO ₂ emissions produced (Mt/y)	+
	CO ₂ storage sites	(I5) Bio CO ₂ emissions produced (Mt/y)	+
		(I6) Total CO ₂ emissions produced (Mt/y)	+
		(I7) Captured CO ₂ emissions (Mt/y)	+
		(I8) Number of plants planed CO ₂ capture	
		(I9) Number of plants planning H2 production	+
		(I10) Number of storage sites	
		(I11) Porosity of the reservoir rocks (average, decimal)	+
		(I12) Permeability of the reservoir rocks (average, Md)	+
		(I13) Well injectivity (Mt/y)	+
		(I14) Thickness of primary cap rocks, m	+
		(I15) CO ₂ storage capacity (total, Mt)	+
CO ₂ transport	(I16) Storage Readiness Level (SRL) (1-9)	+	
	(I17) Transport distance to storage site (min, km)	-	
	(I18) Transport distance to storage site (max, km)	-	
Infrastructure	(I19) Transport distance to storage site total (km)	+	
	(I20) Number of wells in operation	+	
	(I21) Number of old abandoned wells	-	
	(I22) Number of planned PCI projects	+	
CO ₂ use options	(I23) Number of CO ₂ use projects in operation, or R&D	+	
	(I24) Longevity of CO ₂ use products (years)	+	
	(I25) Bio-CO ₂ to be used (Mt)	+	

Table 4-3. Internal assessment score in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions

	Internal assesment key factors	U nit	Pola -rity	B1	B2	B3	B4	Balt- Total/ Avg*	M1	M2		M3	M4	Med- Total/ Avg*
I1	Number of countries	N	+	2	3	3	1	9/ 2.3	2	2		1	2	7/ 1.8
I2	Number of clusters	N	+	3	9	4	4	20/5	2	3		1	6	12/3
I3	Number of plants	N	+	6	33	16	11	67/17	16	32		2	32	82/21
I4	Fossil CO ₂ emissions produced	Mt /y	+	4.25	12.08	4.55	8.03	28.9/ 7.2	40	22.75		0.59 6	41. 1	62.8/ 31.4

D.3.3 A generic framework for selection of the most promising CCUS value chains

I5	Bio CO ₂ emissions produced	Mt /y	+	0	8.06	1.36	0.16	9.6/2.4	0	1.07		0.57 2	0	1.6/ 0.6
I6	Total CO ₂ emissions produced	Mt /y	+	4.25	22.66	5.91	8.19	41.2/ 10.3	40	23.82		1.17	41.1	106/ 26.5
I7	Captured annual CO ₂ emissions	Mt /y	+	4.04	20.14	5.62	7.78	37.6/ 9.4	18.6 4	9.77		0.83 3	18.4 7	47.7/ 11.93
I8	N. of plants planning CO ₂ capture	N	+	4	18	9	3	34/ 8.5	0	22		0	0	23/ 5.5
I9	No. of plants planning hydrogen production or in operation	N	+	2	2	2	4	10/2.5	0	2		0	0	2/ 0.7
I10	Number of storage sites	N	-	-3	-8	-3	-2	16/4	-1	-1		-1	-1	4/1
I11	Porosity of the reservoir rocks	De ci mal	+	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.18	/0.2	0.2	0.18		0.15	0.25	/0.22
I12	Permeability of reservoir rocks	m D	+	530	400	325	350	/401	50	500		300	300	/217
I13	Well injectivity	Mt /y	+	1	0.41	0.35	0.8	/0.64	0.5	1.09		0.8	0.8	/0.8
I14	Thickness of primary cap rocks	m	+	48.7	150	180	150	/132	800*	900*		115	71	/329
I15	CO ₂ storage capacity	Mt	+	402.6	928	657	381	2369/ 592	135 0	200		34	860	2444/ 611
I16	Storage Readiness Level (SRL)	N	+	3.33	3	3	2	11.3/2. 83	1	2		2	2	7/1.7 5
I17	Transport distance to storage site (min)	k m	-	-10	-5	-5	-4.2	/6.05	-120	-48		-32.6	-50	/62.7
I18	Transport distance to storage site (max)	km	-	-145	-750	-200	- 38.2	1133/2 83.3	-360	-470		-38.5	-900	/442
I19	Transport distance to storage site (total)	km	-	-283	-2830	-460	-108	3681/ 920.3	- 649, 6	-520		-38.5	- 141 3	2621. 4/657

I2 0	N of wells in operation	N	+	6	18	19	0	43/10.8	3	0		0	0	3/0.8
I2 1	N of abandoned old wells	N	-	-21	-6	-2	-5	34/8.5	-0	-12		-5	-1	18/4.5
I2 2	N of planned PCI projects	N	+	1	2	1	1	5/1.25	1	1		0	0	2/0.5
I2 3	N of CO ₂ use projects in operation, R&D	N	+	1	8	3	1	13/3.3	2	3		0	0	5/1.3
I2 4	Longevity of CO ₂ use products	Ye ars	+	1	1	1	1	/1	1	1		1	1	/1
I2 5	Bio-CO ₂ to be used	Mt	+	0.4	6.05	0.56	0.78	7.8/2.0	5.59	2.93		0.25	5.54	14.3/2.9

Total/Avg* -Total and Average numbers for the region are calculated if suitable. If Total value is not suitable, then only Average is shown as /Average.

4.3 External Factors Assessment in two regions

The external technical risks analysed for the (1) storage site area: storage site located in the densely populated area, storage site area belonging to landlords, storage site located in seismic risk area, or in Natura 2000 area/other protected area.

Table 4-4 External technical factors and their location

EXTERNAL FACTORS	Location
Storage site located in the densely populated area (onshore): Low – 1, medium – 2–3, high – 5	Onshore
Storage site area belonging to landlords (Yes - 5, No -1)	Onshore
Storage site located in seismic risk area (no seismic risk – 1, low seismic risk – 2, seismic risk in the neighbouring region – 3, average seismic risk – 4, high seismic risk - 5)	Onshore and offshore
Storage site located in Natura 2000 area/other protected area (100% located in the protected area - 5, 50% located in the protected area -4, 25% -3, 10% -2, not located -1)	Onshore and offshore
Transport routes is going through Natura 2000 area/other protected area (100% located in the protected area - 5, 50% located in the protected area -4, 25% -3, 10% -2, not located -1)	Onshore and offshore

In the non-technical groups social and regulatory (2, 3) the analysed factors were: public acceptance, political development, status under the London Protocol and Amendment to Article 6, application of the EU CCS Directive, national permission for CO₂ storage. For MRV and financial groups (4, 5) the following parameters were analysed: MRV and accounting readiness, and availability of the government financial support along the value chain.

We created the hierarchy of the analysis on external assessment (Table 4-5), where the qualitative and quantitative parameters should be assigned from 1 to 5.

Table 4-5. Factors considered in the non-technical aspects of the external group of SWOT analysis

Group	Aspects	Factors	Polarity
External assessment	Public acceptance	(E1) Level of public acceptance (low - 1, medium - 3, high - 5)	+
	Political development	(E2) Favourable - 4-5, Business as usual - 2-3, Unfavourable - 1	+
	International Regulations	(E3) London Protocol (LP): Non member - 1, Member of London Convention - 2, Member of LP - 3, Amendment to Article 6 implemented - 4, Provisional Application of Article 6 to LP - 5	+
	National regulations	(E4) EU CCS Directive implemented: CO ₂ storage permitted for research - 1; CO ₂ storage: permitted offshore - 3, permitted onshore - 3, permitted onshore and offshore - 5	+
	MRV (Monitoring Reporting and Verification)	(E5) MRV Readiness: Low - 1, Medium - 3, High - 5	+
		(E6) Accounting Readiness: Low - 1, Medium - 3, High-5	+
	Business Model	(E7) Governmental financial support for CCUS projects: Not available - 1, available, but low - 2, available but could be higher - 3, available significantly - 5	
	Readiness of CCUS value chain	(E8) Value chain readiness: Developing Capture -1, Capture available -2, Developing Capture & Transport - 2, Capture and transport available - 4, Developing Capture, transport and storage - 3, Capture, transport and storage available - 5, Capture in development, storage is available - 3,	+
Interaction with other decarbonization technologies	(E9) CCUS in Industrial strategy/plan: Yes - 5, No - 2, No strategy/plan - 1	+	

Table 4-6. Factors considered in the technical aspects (the area around the storage site) of the external group of SWOT analysis

Group	Aspects	Factors	Polarity
External assessment	Density of population	(E10) Storage site located in the densely populated area Low - 1, medium - 3, high - 5	
	Storage site ownership	(E11) Storage site area belonging to landlords: Yes - 5, No - 1	-
	Seismicity	(E12) Storage site located in seismic risk area: no seismic risk - 1, low seismic risk - 2, seismic risk in the neighbouring region - 3, average seismic risk - 4, high seismic risk - 5	-
		(E13) Storage site located in Natura 2000 area/other protected area: 100% located in the protected area - 5, 50% - 4, 25% - 3, 10% - 2, no located - 1	-
Protected areas	(E14) Transport routes are going through Natura 2000 area/other protected area: 100% located in the protected area - 5, 50% - 4, 25% - 3, 10% - 2, not located - 1	-	

Table 4-7. External assessment score in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions

	External assessment key factors	Polarity	B1	B2	B3	B4	B-Avg	M1	M2	M3	M4	M-Avg
	Non-technical factors											
E1	(E1) Level of public acceptance (low - 1, medium - 3, high - 5)	+	3	3	3	1	2.5	3	3	1	1	2
E2	(E2) Favourable - 4-5, Business as usual - 2-3, Unfavourable - 1	+	2	4	4	3	3.25	2	3	3	1	2.25
E3	(E3) London Protocol (LP): Non member - 1, Member of London Convention - 2, Member of LP - 3, Amendment to Article 6 implemented - 4, Provisional Application of Article 6 to LP - 5	+	NA	4.3	4.3	NA	4.3	1.5	3	NA	2.5	2.33
E4	(E4) EU CCS Directive implemented: CO2 storage permitted for research - 1; CO2 storage: permitted offshore - 3, permitted onshore - 3, permitted onshore and offshore with limitations - 4, permitted onshore and offshore - 5		1	5	5	3	3.5	4	5	5	4	4.5
E5	(E5) MRV Readiness: Low - 1, Medium - 3, High - 5	+	1	5	5	1	3	1	1	3	1	1.5
E6	(E6) Accounting Readiness: Low - 1, Medium - 3, High-5	+	1	5	5	1	3	1	3	3	3	2.5
E7	(E7) Governmental financial support for CCUS projects: Not available - 1, available, but low - 2, available but could be higher - 3, available significantly - 5	+	1	3	3	1	2	2	1	1	2	1.5
E8	(E8) Value chain readiness: Developing Capture -1, Capture available -2, Developing Capture & Transport - 2, Development Capture and Storage-2, Capture and transport available - 4, Developing Capture, transport and storage - 3, Capture, transport and storage available - 5, Capture in development, storage is available - 3,	+	1	3	3	2	2.25	1.5	4	3	3	2.88
E9	(E9) CCUS in Industrial strategy/plan: Yes - 5, No - 2, No strategy/plan - 1	+	1	3.7	3.7	1	2.35	3.5	3.5	2	5	3.5

	Technical factors		B1	B2	B3	B4	B-Avg	M1	M2	M3	M4	M-Avg
E10	Storage site located in the densely populated area (onshore): Low – 1, medium – 2–3, high – 5	-	-2	-3	-3	-2	-2.5	NA	NA	-2	-1	-1.5
E11	Storage site area belonging to landlords (Yes - 5, No -1)	-	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	NA	NA	-1	-4	-2.5
E12	Storage site located in seismic risk area (no seismic risk – 1, low seismic risk – 2, seismic risk in the neighbouring region – 3, average seismic risk – 4, high seismic risk - 5	-	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-3	-2	-1	-2	-2
E13	Storage site located in Natura 2000 area/other protected area (100% located in the protected area - 5, 50% located in the protected area -4, 25% -3, 10% -2, not located -1)	-	-2	-1	-3	-1	-1.75	-3	-5	-5	-2	-3.75
E14	Transport routes is going through Natura 2000 area/other protected area (100% located in the protected area - 5, 50% located in the protected area -4, 25% -3, 10% -2, not located -1)	-	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2	-2	-4	-1	-2.25

4.4 Integration of technical and nontechnical factors

The most important factors influencing CCUS value chains in terms of SWOT analysis are developed based on technical and nontechnical parameters organised as internal and external SWOT factors and integrated in the Table 4-8.

Table 4-8 The most important factors influencing CCUS value chains in terms of SWOT analysis

	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
INTERNAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International cooperation (I-1) High impact on climate change (I-4 - I-7) Cooperation with renewables and energy storage (I-9) Sufficient storage capacity justified by injection tests (I-11, I-15) Sufficient injectivity (I12-I13) Safety of storage site justified by geological data or experience (I14, I21) CO₂ storage site exploration license is executed and storage site explored CO₂ Storage licences are available CCUS PCI projects under development (I-22) Bio CO₂ is available for utilization and storage (I-25) CO₂ use projects (in development or operation) (I-23) Possibility to reuse infrastructure (I-20) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low level of national cooperation in clusters (I-2, I-3) Low readiness of emitters (I-8) Scarce geological data about the storage site Theoretical storage capacity Low readiness of the storage sites (I-16) High risk of CO₂ leakage Distant location from emitters to storage site (I7-I9) Bio CO₂ is not yet reported (I-25) CO₂ use options are not developed or projects stoped caused by high costs of production

	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
EXTERNAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Political support of CCUS (E-2) International and national CCS regulations implemented (E-3) CO₂ storage is permitted onshore and offshore (E4) Governmental financial support is available (E7) CO₂ capture, transport and storage are under development (E-8) CCUS included in the national industrial strategy plans (E-9) MRV and accounting readiness are high 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low public acceptance (E-1, E-10) CCUS is not included in NECP (National Energy and Climate plans) Any CO₂ injections banned Regional conventions do not include CCS regulations, or banning CO₂ injection CO₂ leakage to other countries (energy is exported from other countries, while national plants are closed, and CCS is not applied). Landlords refuse to cooperate (E-11) Seismic risks in southern countries E12) Location of storage sites and transport corridors in the protected areas (E12-14)

5 Discussion

A generic framework for the selection of the most prospective CCUS value chains at the very early stage of their development, based on the high-level screening methodology established in WP1 and integrated with WP2 analyses, is presented in this report.

A semi-quantitative SWOT analyses, based on internal technical parameters and external technical and non-technical parameters was performed for 8 proposed in D1.2 value chains in two regions. The most important SWOT factors influencing CCUS value chains was proposed in terms of SWOT analysis.

A framework for quantitative SWOT analyses were developed, where the concept of Multiple-Attribute Decision Making (MADM), using a multi-layer scheme to simplify complicated problems could be applied. Weights of key factors can be calculated by using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP).

From 8 CCUS value chains selected in D1.2 for further analysis in WP3, two the most promising projects were selected for the further techno-economic modelling and business case in the WP4 – Baltic-2 in the Baltic Sea Region, and Med-2 in the Mediterranean Sea Region.

The Baltic-2 projects was selected, based on its highest impact on climate change and the highest level of readiness in the Baltic Region, including 2 PCI projects ongoing, the highest level of development of CO₂ use options, the highest national and international regulatory readiness for CO₂ storage in Denmark and started CO₂ injections in two DOFs. However, among weakness of this value chain could be mentioned the highest total transport distance and a relatively high number of storage sites (8), which can cause the increase in transport and storage costs compared to the closer located and larger storage sites.

The Baltic-1 (Latvia and Lithuania) and Baltic-4 (Northern Poland) value chains are categorised as less ready due to regulatory risks associated with CO₂ storage onshore in Latvia and Poland. Despite the planned changes in the CCS regulations and other available technical strengths, these regulatory changes in Latvia and Poland may take additional time, and these risks should be seriously considered. Regulatory situation is more advanced in Poland, where CO₂ storage offshore is already permitted at national level and the law to permit onshore storage is under development.

The Mediterranean-2 project (France and Spain) was selected for the further techno-economic modelling and business case in WP4, based on its relatively high level of readiness and impact on climate change in the Mediterranean Region. M-4 project (Italy and Greece) has lower readiness and M-1 project (Turkey and Greece) has the lowest readiness, and they both have seismic risks, despite higher impact on climate change compared to M-2 and M-1 project suffered from the lack of CCS regulations in Turkey.

In general, the Mediterranean Sea Region is looking as less ready than the Baltic Region, comparing its total and average numbers of the internal technical and external technical and non-technical factors.

Four Baltic value chains include 6 countries and 20 clusters versus 5 countries and 12 clusters in four Mediterranean projects. The total and average number of plants and CO₂ emissions produced and captured are higher in the Mediterranean projects, while reported bio-CO₂ emissions is higher in the Baltic projects. The number of planned H₂ production projects/or in operation is 10 in Baltic versus 2 in the Mediterranean value chains.

4 PCI projects in the Baltic versus 2 in the Mediterranean, already started CO₂ injection and other developments in Denmark, the high amount of CO₂ use projects under development in Denmark, Sweden and Germany versus lower number in the Mediterranean region also create different levels of CCUS readiness in two regions.

The storage sites in two regions were compared by key parameters. The Storage Readiness Level (SRL) is significantly higher both in total and average numbers in Baltic versus Mediterranean Region, while total and average storage capacity are in the same range in two regions (total capacity is 2.37 Gt in Baltic and 2.44 Gt in Mediterranean). Number of storage sites is 4 times higher in Baltic, that is evidence that costs for storage sites development and operation will be higher in the Baltic Region. The quality of the storage sites was high enough in both regions except for the Med-3 project. The average well injectivity was estimated slightly higher in the Mediterranean region but considering very conservative estimates of injectivity in the Danish storage sites, this difference is not significant for the project's development.

The safety of the storage sites could be assessed by thickness of the primary cap rocks and number of abandoned wells, which could be the way for CO₂ leakage. However, in Med-1 and Med-2 projects the thickness of primary rocks are not known as the thickness of primary and secondary cap rocks were estimated together as 800 and 900 m correspondingly.

The total number of abandoned and in operation wells is correspondingly 2 and 14 times higher in the Baltic compared to Mediterranean Region. The high number of abandoned wells in the Baltic Region can be estimated as weakness through the higher risks of leakage, while the high number of wells in operation gives an economic strength for infrastructure reusing, especially at the early stages of project development. The minimum and maximum transport distances from CO₂ emitters to storage sites were lower in the Baltic projects, while total distance was higher, explained by higher number of storage sites and more countries involved in the Baltic projects. The possibility of reusing infrastructure is available in the Baltic-2 value chain, where Greensand and Bifrost storage sites in DOF are already demonstrating the reuse of the available infrastructure. Such option could be available in the Mediterranean Region in the Prinos storage site in the Med-1 project. However, reusing of available infrastructure in the Prinos is planned for the DOFs, while Med-1 project is planning CO₂ storage in the Prinos DSA in the deeper layer, and most probable, reusing of infrastructure will be not possible.

As it is already reported in chapter 2.2.2, the most prospective CO₂ use options were analysed in several recent publications. CO₂ products permitting use the most captured CO₂ is Syntetic Liquefied Fuel (synfuel) (8447 Mt/y), CO₂ based Methane (6309 Mt/y) and syngas (1251 Mt/y).

However, all these products have low retention time (1 year assigned). However, this time is the same as for conventional fossil-based products, but they become environmentally friendly when produced from bio-CO₂. It is complicated to estimate their revenues, because their production price using renewable energy, is too high now and very uncertain, but will be decreased with decreasing costs for renewable energy and wide industrial implementation. Production of these products could be considered as one of the options for renewable energy storage, when it is produced to excess of the present needs. The most prospective CO₂ use option from the point of view of long retention time is CO₂ mineral carbonation, which could be suitable for the cement plants included in most of our scenarios. However exact planning of this option is complicated now, when plants did not yet report developments in this direction.

The proposed value chains have various, but in general good prospect for production of these renewable CO₂ use products. The Baltic Region projects and Baltic-2 value chain has the highest number of CO₂ use project in demonstration and development phases, however the high costs of the production make the risks for delay in these technologies' implementation. The cheaper production costs are possible when by-products and energy from waste, or waste energy could be applied for production.

The external non-technical factors (SWOT opportunities) are more favourable in the Baltic Region. The level of public acceptance is rather medium in the Baltic Region, and low to medium in the Mediterranean Region. Political development is also more favourable in Baltics and rather „Business as usual” in Mediterranean Region. International regulations needed for export of CO₂ for offshore storage is already implemented in Denmark, but not yet in Spain and Greece, while Italy is planning to implement. In average CCS Directive is implemented equally in two regions, but CO₂ storage is permitted nationally in all Mediterranean projects, while not permitted in Latvia and onshore Poland in the Baltics. Therefore, the highest regulatory threats are evaluated now for offshore storage in the Mediterranean Region and for onshore storage in Latvia.

The MRV and accounting readiness and governmental financial support for CCUS projects are available now for the Baltic-2 and Baltic-3 projects, while average value chain readiness is the same in two regions.

The last nontechnical factor (CCUS in industrial strategy/plan) has a higher average score for the Mediterranean Region. The last two non-technical parameters is an evidence of opportunities in both regions.

The nontechnical external factors create threats at national level, but at the same time gave opportunity to national governments to implement needed CCUS regulations, policies and support CCUS technology at various levels (national, federal, regional and international).

The first (E10) and second (E11) external technical factors create threats only for onshore projects and had lower score for the Baltic Region (4 projects with onshore storage) and higher for the Mediterranean Region (2 projects with onshore storage). The third factor (E12) seismic risk is a real threat for the Mediterranean Region, according to its location in geologically active seismic regions and recent experience with earthquakes. The next two factors (E13 - Storage site located in Natura 2000 area/other protected area and E-14 Transport routes is going through Natura 2000 area/other protected area) had higher threats for the Mediterranean Region.

We analysed together 8 projects from two sea regions. Among them we have projects with various locations of storage sites and CO₂ transport from emission clusters, including three projects with onshore transport and storage (B-1, B-4, and M-3), two projects with onshore and offshore transport and offshore storage (M-1 and M-2), one project with onshore and offshore

transport and onshore storage (M-4), B-3 project with mainly onshore transport and storage and one nearshore storage site, and finally B2-project, which includes both onshore and offshore storage sites and transport options.

Considering the high variability and complexity of the selected value chains, it is not possible quantitatively analyse all of them together using all the proposed technical and nontechnical factors. However, the shortlist of the commonly proposed factors could be applied.

6 Conclusions

The developed framework includes 25 internal quantitative technical parameters and 14 external qualitative parameters, which were collected for eight CCUS value chains in two sea regions. These internal and external parameters were the base for creating a SWOT matrix of CCUS value chains strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. For the qualitative parameters, an equivalent quantitative scaling method was designed to be able to include external parameters in the quantitative SWOT analysis.

However, the export of CO₂ to offshore storage sites needs CO₂ storage regulations to be implemented internationally (London Protocol Amendment to article 6) and regionally (Helsinki and Barcelona Conventions), in addition to national regulations and permits needed for CO₂ storage both in onshore and offshore sites.

Despite these differences and differences in the external technical parameters, it is possible to perform a unified quantitative analysis for all projects (both onshore and offshore) by utilising common internal technical factors and a shortlist of external technical and non-technical parameters.

Here, we reported the semiquantitative results of the analysis for the projects at very early stage of development, the framework for the quantitative SWOT analysis, and data collected for quantitative analysis.

All the proposed CCUS value chains have future opportunities for implementation but need a considerable amount of work to be done starting from international and national political cooperation and development, regulatory and permitting changes, CCUS technologies development and implementation, cooperation of national stakeholders and governmental support of CCUS value chains. Cooperation with other technologies is also needed. The number of CCS PCI projects already available in both studied regions is a good base start for the possible development and implementation of the proposed CCUS value chains.

7 Reference List

- Akhurst M., Kirk K., Neele F., Grimstad I.-A., Bentham M., Bergmo P., (2021). Storage Readiness Levels: communicating the maturity of site technical understanding, permitting and planning needed for storage operations using CO₂, *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, Volume 110, 103402, ISSN 1750-5836, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2021.103402>
- Bosshart N.W, Azzolina N.A, Ayash S.C, Peck W.D, Gorecki C.D, Ge J, Jiang T, Dotzenrod N.W., (2018). Quantifying the effects of depositional environment on deep saline formation CO₂ storage efficiency and rate. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*. Vol 69, p.8-19.
- Carneiro, J.F., and Mesquita, P., (2020). Key data for characterising sources, transport options, storage and uses in promising regions. EU H2020 STRATEGY CCUS Project 837754, Report, pp 170.
- Chang H. & Huang W., (2006). Application of a quantification SWOT analytical method. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, Vol. 43, 1-2, Elsevier,158-169, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcm.2005.08.016>
- Chauvy, R., Meunier, N., Thomas, D., De Weireld, G., 2019. Selecting emerging CO₂ utilization products for short- to mid-term deployment. *Appl. Energy* 236, 662–680. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.11.096>.
- CO2Fokus, (2024), <https://www.co2fokus.eu/project/>, assessed on 9.12.2024
- COZMOS, (2024), COZMOS Project, CO₂ Value Europe Portal, [CCU Projects Database \(co2value.eu\)](https://www.co2value.eu/), assessed on 16.12.2024.
- Decreto-Legge n. 181, (2023), Disposizioni urgenti per la sicurezza energetica del Paese, la materia di ricostruzione nei territori colpiti dagli eccezionali eventi alluvionali verificatisi a partire dal 1° maggio 2023. (23G00195) [\(GU Serie Generale n.287 del 09-12-2023\)](https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2023/12/09/23G00195/sg/). Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana, 2023-12-9, <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2023/12/09/23G00195/sg/>.
- ENI, (2024). Carbon capture, transport, storage and utilization, CO₂ also as a resource, <https://www.eni.com/en-IT/actions/energy-transition-technologies/carbon-capture-utilization-storage.html>.
- European Commission, (2019). Directorate-General for Climate Action, Turnau, S., Jaspers, D., Marxen, A., Naims, H. et al., Identification and analysis of promising carbon capture and utilisation technologies, including their regulatory aspects – Final report, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2834/348288>
- Grataloup S., Coueffe R., Tourlière B., Le Thiez P., (2012). Identification des sites potentiels de stockage de CO₂ et première estimations des capacités. PROJET VASCO – Phase 5 : Stockage en aquifères salins - Tache 5.2. Rapport final. BRGM/RP-64302-FR, 63pp.
- Gravaud, I., Shogenova, A., Shogenov, K., Sousa, L.H., Wójcicki, A., Lothe, A.E., Cruard, Q., Sinayuç, Ç., Yıldırım, B., Bulbul, S., Stevenson, R. & Perimenis, A., (2024). Deliverable 1.2 Identification of promising CCUS value chains in the two ZEN regions for further analyses in WP3. Open report in EU Horizon Europe CCUS ZEN. Project 101075693.
- HERCCULES, (2024). Horizon Europe HERCCULES project, <https://www.herccules.eu/about-herccules/project-overview>
- Honegger, M., Oh, S., Schmitt, F., Poralla, M., Ombudstvedt, I., Ostgaard, L., Viguier, R., Palfi, E., Bell, R., Evensen, D., Chalmers, H., Karimi, F. & Dahlberg, U., (2024), Making CCU and CCS hubs and clusters happen: Overcoming non-technical challenges. Perspectives Climate Research on behalf of the CCUS ZEN Project, D2.3 of CCUS ZEN project, Freiburg i.B., Germany, 70 pp.
- IGME, (2024). <https://info.igme.es/Hidrocarburos/>
- INECP-Italy. (2024). Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security of Italy. National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate by 2021-2030, July 2024, 490 pp. [National energy and climate plans \(europa.eu\)](https://www.europa.eu/national-energy-and-climate-plans)
- INNO-CCUS. (2023). State of CCUS. Danish research and innovation driving CCUS solutions to combat climate change, 147 pp.
- IRENA AND METHANOL INSTITUTE, (2021), Innovation Outlook: Renewable Methanol, International Renewable Energy Agen, 124 pp.
- LRV.LT, (2024), <https://sumin.lrv.lt/en/news/minister-skuodis-to-open-the-international-e-fuels-conference-in-berlin-to-sign-a-declaration-on-e-fuels-in-mobility/>

P2XEurope, (2022), <https://www.p2x-europe.com/news/detail/new-power-to-liquid-plant-at-hrs-hamburg-site-produces-alternatives-to-fossil-raw-materials/>

RECODE, (2024), Recycling carbon dioxide in the cement industry to produce added-value additives: a step towards a CO2 circular economy (RECODE), <https://recodeh2020.eu/index.html>

REVE, 2024. Spain has 29 projects from the EU Innovation Fund, with more than 1,286 million in aid, (<https://www.evwind.es/2024/12/27/spain-has-29-projects-from-the-eu-innovation-fund-with-more-than-1286-million-in-aid/103509>).

Ringstad, C., Falck da Silva, E., Skagestad, R., Heyn, R., Biragnet, C., Frykman P., Anthonsen, K.L., Gravaud, I., Wójcicki, A., Shogenova, A., Shogenov, K., Sınayuç, Ç., Yıldırım, B., Bulbul, S., Sousa, L.H. & Perimenis, A., (2023). Deliverable 1.1: High-level regional mapping of CO2 emission sources utilization industry and infrastructure in the Baltic Sea and Mediterranean Sea regions. Zero Emission Network to facilitate CCUS uptake in industrial clusters. CCUS ZEN. Open report in EU Horizon Europe CCUS ZEN. Project 101075693.

Rojas-Michaga, M.F., Michailos, S., Cardozo, E., Akram, M., Kevin Hughes, K., Ingham, D., Pourkashanian, M., (2023). Sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) production through power-to-liquid (PtL): A combined techno-economic and life cycle assessment, *Energy Conversion and Management* 292, 117427, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.117427>

S&P Global, (2024), <https://www.spglobal.com/commodityinsights/en/market-insights/latest-news/energy-transition/081524-orsted-scraps-swedish-flagshipone-e-methanol-project-under-development>

Shogenova, A., Shogenov, K., Sousa, L.H., Bonto, M., Gravaud, I., Lopez, A., Koumentis, I., Sınayuç, Ç., Yıldırım, B., Bulbul, S., Frykman P., Anthonsen, K.L., Bouvier, L., Lothe, A., Wójcicki, A., Perimenis, A., Ombudstvedt, I., Warmer, L., Honegger, M., Karimi, F., & Marzban, E., (2025), Deliverable 3.1 CCUS value chains for the two CCUS ZEN regions selected for further development in WP4. Open report in EU Horizon Europe CCUS ZEN. Project 101075693.

Shokrollahi M., Teymouri, N., Navarri, P., (2024). Identification and evaluation of most promising CO2 technologies: Multi criteria decision analysis and techno-economic assessment. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 434, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139620>

Skypower, (2024), https://project-skypower.org/sites/default/files/2024-10/Project%20SkyPower%20Insights%20Report%20October%202024_final.pdf

Sollai S., Porcu A., Tola V., Ferrara F., Pettinau A. (2023) Renewable methanol production from green hydrogen and captured CO2: A techno-economic assessment, *Journal of CO2 Utilization* 68, 102345, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2022.102345>

WLPGA, (2019), World Liquid Gas Annual Report 2019, 56 pp, [WLPGA-Annual-Report-2019.pdf](#)